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**IFMIS, a hit or miss?
Government agents' perception
analysis of the Integrated
Financial and Management
Information System (IFMIS) in
the Philippines**

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Preface

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BTMS	Budget Treasury Management System
BTr	Bureau of the Treasury
COA	Commission on Audit
DBM	Department of Budget and Management
DepEd	Department of Education
DND	Department of National Defense
DOF	Department of Finance
DSWD	Department of Social Welfare and Development
DTI	Department of Trade and Industry
GIFMIS	Government Integrated Financial Management Information System
IFMIS	Integrated Financial Management Information System
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IT	Information Technology
OTS	Off-the-shelf
PEFA	Public Expenditure Financial Accountability
PFM	Public Financial Management
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TSA	Treasury Single Account
UACS	Unified Account Code Structure
UN	United Nations
WB	World Bank

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Effective Public Financial Management (PFM) is a cornerstone of good governance and is crucial in realizing sustainable development goals (Hirsch,2017). PFM shows where taxes go or how public finances are collected, spent, and accounted for. However, PFM in developing countries remains ineffective in securing long-term economic growth and ensuring transparency and accountability in managing government resources. Reforming PFM has also been complex and costly. PFM reform's outcome is embellished with complex factors which have intrigued researchers and practitioners alike. Among such reforms that get the most attention is establishing an Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS), which is said to be a fundamental building block of the PFM system.

While IFMIS has been studied well in Africa, few studies have been conducted in Southeast Asia, and rare academic case studies have been conducted in the Philippines. The idea of IFMIS has been around the country for decades, but its development has slowly progressed. It failed to get a green light with several disapprovals in previous government administrations, and the Budget Treasury Management System (BTMS), the scaled-down version of IFMIS, was recently suspended. With the impending relaunch of BTMS by the new administration, the perception of agents/end-users on the implementation of IFMIS/BTMS remains understudied.

This research builds on the institutional change theory espoused by Andrews (2014) and tests his hypotheses on the variation of agents' support for PFM reforms, using the Philippines' IFMIS as a case study to supplement the literature gap. In this research, the following questions are explored: (1) *How do the perceptions in IFMIS implementation between **distributed agents** (government employees in the line/implementing agencies) and **concentrated agents** (government employees in PFM agencies) differ given the following reform conditions: (a) disrupted context, (b) legitimacy of incumbent rules/processes (existing institutions), (c) viability of reform alternatives, and (d) active engagement of agents in the reform design?* (2) *What factors explain the difference and its influence on implementing IFMIS?*

We employed action research with a mixed method case study design to capture the diverse dimensions of the above topic and hypotheses. A survey was administered among 267 concentrated and distributed agents from selected national government agencies in the Philippines

identified through non-probability sampling. The researcher coiled a 22 5-pt Likert scale questionnaire to evaluate whether there is a statistically significant difference in agents' perceptions on the IFMIS implementation vis-a-vis reform conditions. Thematic analysis of key informant interviews and open-ended questionnaires, using a purposively identified subset of the two groups, complemented the quantitative approach.

Survey results show patterns that contribute to understanding the difference and similarity between the two types of agents and how they perceived IFMIS as a PFM reform. Of the 22 variables studied, results revealed statistical significance in the difference of perception in four variables, which means that the hypotheses were confirmed in the following conditions: (1) distributed agents were less likely to agree than concentrated agents that context is disrupted; (2) distributed agents doubt the viability of the BTMS because of agency resistance and (3) need for legislation; and (4) distributed agents were not given enough time to implement the reform. This study found no statistically significant difference from the other 18 variables. However, eight variables tested in this research showed that distributed agents would support the IFMIS/BTMS more than the concentrated agents, contrary to Andrews' hypotheses. The qualitative interviews highlighted several factors that explain result deviation. The study found cultural norms in the workplace, i.e., close-knit family ties and highly valued transactional relationships, present among the respondents that partially explained the results. These nuances indicate that it is complicated to label certain group characteristics without being restrictive, particularly with government personnel whose functions often overlap. Further investigation identified several main factors that limited the success of IFMIS in the country: (1) lack of political will, (2) lack of ownership among concentrated agencies, and (3) the problematic purchase of off-the-shelf BTMS, and (4) poor management strategy.

However, findings taken as a whole were indicative rather than conclusive. Methodological limitations given purposive sampling suggest results which cannot be generalized and are not representative of all government agents. Nonetheless, we hope that these limitations will be mitigated through subsequent action research with improved methodology. This research may serve as a blueprint for more case studies and reference for policy-makers to deepen their understanding of how agents contribute to the success of IFMIS or any other PFM reform. We must recognize the importance of learning from past lessons to improve future policies. It may be a hit or miss, success or failure, but we must continuously try and get better each time.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Contextual setting

Effective Public Financial Management (PFM) is a cornerstone of good governance and is crucial in realizing sustainable development goals (SDGs, Hirsch, 2017). PFM shows where taxes go or how public finances are collected, spent, and accounted for. It covers a “[...]set of laws, rules, systems, and processes used by sovereign nations (and sub-national governments), to mobilize revenue, allocate public funds, undertake public spending, account for funds and audit results” (Lawson,2015, p.1). A robust PFM enhances accountability and governance and “is associated with efficient and equitable public service delivery, poverty reduction, and economic growth” (James et al., 2022, p.30).

However, PFM in developing countries remains ineffective in securing long-term economic growth and ensuring transparency and accountability in managing government resources. Reforming PFM has been painstakingly difficult and has seen varying outcomes in the past decades, given its inherent complexities, overlapping processes, systems, and institutions (Allen et al.,2013; Andrews et al.,2014; Omollo,2018). Also, PFM reforms have been very costly. Over \$20 billion have been poured in by development agencies alone on PFM reforms (Fritz, 2017). From the time Pretorius and Pretorius (2008) conducted a comprehensive review of the state of PFM reforms from 1998 to 2008, researchers and practitioners have been seeing a similar fluctuating trend of success, failure, regress, and slow progress, in reforming PFM (Fritz et al., 2017). The reason(s) for the confounding results are important but not apparent at the outset. Thereby, exploring the different outcomes and factors that influence PFM reforms is crucial.

Among the PFM reforms that puzzled researchers and practitioners alike concerns the Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS). It is an IT solution that aims to collect and organize financial information of all government agencies for government-wide consolidation in an interlinked and interfaced platform that provides timely and comprehensive information about where public finances go. However, 1/3 of IFMIS reform initiatives are a total failure, and a further half are partial failures. 1/3 are only successfully delivered on time, on budget, and fully meeting user requirements (Stanforth, 2006). PFM reforms are gearing toward maximizing the opportunity to use technology and digitalization of PFM processes to support the huge demands

for additional investments to make a dent with SDGs (Gaspar et al.,2019, Eltokhy,2022). But can IFMIS deliver?

The promises of IFMIS benefits entice governments to implement such reform. “An IFMIS offers governments significant benefits in managing public monies more effectively, including greater financial control, improved monitoring of the government’s cash position and better planning for future requirements, better fiscal reporting, and timely availability of a complete set of data to form a reliable basis for budget formulation” (PEFA, 2016, p.103). IFMIS is a core component and a fundamental building block of the PFM system (Stanforth, 2006). It is a crucial management tool that offers comprehensive financial/non-financial information that can track expenditures and improve transparency and accountability in the budget process (Chêne, 2009, Diamond & Khemani, 2006). According to the World Bank (WB, 2022), as of January 22, 2022, the total project cost for IFMIS is around \$5.8 billion for 122 completed and 25 active IFMIS projects. However, with this expensive innovation, governments must carefully thread its design and implementation.

As early as 2010, the Philippine Government has been working on developing the Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS). This is in response to the PEFA assessment in 2007, which highlighted the gaps of fragmented Information Technology (IT) systems in various PFM processes, cash management, and accounting practices, coupled with the limited capacities of PFM practitioners.¹ Like the trend elsewhere, the IFMIS became the core automation solution in the Philippines public sector.

However, several technological and non-technological factors prevented the government from proceeding with the rollout of GIFMIS as originally planned (DBM,2016). The DBM pursued a minor core system through the Budget Treasury Management System (BTMS, Fritz et al., 2017). The BTMS links budget execution and treasury cash management, among other PFM processes. Unfortunately, after years of pilot and rollout, the DBM announced in 2021 the indefinite suspension of the BTMS because of the changes in the strategic direction of the envisioned IFMIS (BTMS Advisory No.2021-08, 2021).

¹ <https://pfm.gov.ph/pfm-reform-roadmap/genesis-of-the-pfm-reform-roadmap/>

Now, WB representative reiterates the urgent need for an IFMIS as it is the “heart of the public financial management’s digital transformation.”² On July 6, 2022, Budget Secretary Amenah Pangandaman announced the plan to relaunch BTMS. She pointed out: *"we've made headway with our BTMS, but there is so much more we can do to strengthen further our IFMIS"* (Leyco, 2022, p.1).

1.2 Problem Statement

The failure of an e-government project like IFMIS is a real and practical problem because of the opportunity cost of investment vis-a-vis implementation realities. Failure of an IT program undermines the whole sector reform program since it serves as a core component upon which most reforms depend. But what do we know so far about what worked, what has failed, and why? Decisions toward IFMIS implementation should consider these dimensions with critical evaluations. However, in the case of the Philippines, this aspect of IFMIS remains understudied.

The literature has identified several factors that affect IFMIS implementation, but studies were mostly on Africa. The literature displayed an interesting dynamic interplay of technology and people. However, the balance of instituting IFMIS tilts more toward technological achievement than application and function, exacerbated by undue regard for agents/actors using the intended IT solution (Stanforth,2006).

Although Andrews (2014) explored externally-supported PFM reforms and analyzed why success is often limited when agents like budgeters, accountants, and auditors in sector or line ministries are engaged, the implication of this study needs further exploration, particularly if applied to a specific PFM reform like IFMIS in the Philippines. In his study, Andrews (2014) focuses on the concentrated and distributed agents of selected African countries, defined as follows:

- **Concentrated agents** work in units and agencies dedicated to PFM in the central government, located in the treasury and budget departments of Ministries of Finance and procurement bureaus and internal audit units. Their main function is making, enforcing, and providing oversight of PFM functions. In developing countries, they are the ones usually engaging external donors like WB and IMF (Andrews, 2014).

²<https://newsbytes.ph/2021/12/29/integrated-info-system-crucial-in-improving-public-financial-mgmt-in-ph-wb-exec/>

- **Distributed agents** are those “people providing transactional PFM services in agencies and entities across government where PFM is not their main focus” (Andrews,2014, p.10). They include budget officers, accountants, auditors, and PFM systems’ end-users, working in line/sector agencies and units whose main mandate is public service delivery (Whittle et al., 2011).

Andrews’ theory postulates that distributed agents tend to support change "if they think that they face disruption, incumbent institutions are no longer legitimate, and alternatives offered in reforms are viable, and if they are actively engaged in making things happen" (Andrews,2014, p.10). He found out that distributed agents limit the PFM reform success in Eastern and Southern African countries. If the above theory is applied in the case of the Philippines' IFMIS, will the result be the same?

With few formal studies conducted on how the varying perceptions between concentrated and distributed agents influence the outcome of IFMIS, this research attempts to fill this gap by examining the theory espoused by Andrews applied in the Philippine setting. With the impending relaunch of IFMIS/BTMS in the Philippines, a reform that has seemingly failed twice to date, this research is of critical importance.

1.3 Research Question

Within this background, we set out to answer the following questions:

- (1) How do the perceptions in IFMIS between **concentrated agents** (employees from the DBM, DOF, BTr, and CoA - members of the PFM committee) and **distributed agents** (budget officers, accountants, auditors from various line agencies) differ given the following study hypotheses (reform conditions):
 - a. Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than concentrated agents to agree that the **context is disrupted by PFM-specific problems**;
 - b. Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than the concentrated agents to agree that the **incumbent PFM rules have lost legitimacy**;
 - c. Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than concentrated agents to consider **IFMIS as a legitimate and practical reform alternative**;

d. Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than concentrated agents to be **engaged in IFMIS design**.

(2) What factors explain the difference and its influence on implementing IFMIS?

1.4 Research objective

This research contributes to the growing literature on IFMIS, particularly on the complexities of the Philippines' experience. Specifically, the objectives are as follows:

- (1) To determine perception differences in IFMIS implementation between concentrated and distributed agents;
- (2) To validate the hypotheses on distributed agents often limiting PFM reform success using the Philippines' IFMIS experience;
- (3) To generate operationally relevant findings, identify opportunities for improvement, and highlight lessons from the IFMIS experience as a guide for would-be reformers, PFM decision-makers, and PFM practitioners/researchers.

1.5 Significance of the study

The study and its findings will be beneficial to the following:

- (1) **PFM Committee Member-agencies/ PFM oversight/ Concentrated Agents.** This study explores the various factors to be considered for a successful PFM reform implementation which may encompass other PFM reforms aside from IFMIS. The study's findings may guide how concentrated agents should be engaged and how PFM reforms should be administered.
- (2) **Distributed Agents/Implementing agencies/End-users.** This study highlights the need to properly engage distributed agents and their importance in a holistic reform approach. The study's findings may encourage strengthened collaboration with concentrated agents to maximize the benefits of existing and future reforms.
- (3) **Donor agencies/ International community.** This study provides a reference case study on how to approach partner governments to make meaningful interventions given the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness. PFM reforms such as IFMIS build effective country governance that maximizes possibilities to achieve SDGs. The attainment of sustainable goals is premised on using better data, big data, real-time, more reliable, and high-quality data (UN, 2019). IFMIS, among other innovations, can greatly help in this endeavor.

- (4) **Software developers and vendors.** This study may reference factors that need to be incorporated in designing a system, particularly on the inputs from the end-user's perspectives.
- (5) **Researchers and academia.** This study aims to serve as a reference for other researchers and academia to undertake similar studies to fill the literature gap and strengthen theoretical approaches to understanding national government policies, programs, and projects.
- (6) **Theory and practice.** This study hopes to facilitate the development and validation of theories in the field of PFM reforms. The study's ideas may serve as a reference to develop better ways of evaluating group thinking and their influence on public sector reform programs.

1.6 Scope and limitation

The Philippines' IFMIS through the BTMS, its scaled-down version³, is only the major PFM reform in the country that is a beneficiary of a World Bank Reimbursable Advisory Service (RAS) (WB Report No. 143605-PH), which qualifies it as externally-supported PFM reform in line with Andrews' study.

The current study does not aim to do the following: (a) comprehensively examine IFMIS technicalities, (b) identify all factors involved in the process, and (c) prescribe holistic solutions that would guarantee the success of IFMIS implementation or any particular PFM reform. This undertaking attempts to highlight several factors that influence the outcome of IFMIS as a PFM reform and use such determinants to enhance and provide a deeper understanding of IFMIS as we investigate the different perceptions of concentrated and distributed agents in the implementation of the IFMIS in the Philippines.

1.7 Structure of the paper

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Chapter 2 provided the literature review of what we know so far about the research topic; Chapter 3 tackled the research framework and methodology; Chapter 4 presented the Philippines IFMIS' experience; Chapter 5 provided the findings and analysis; and Chapter 6 offered summary, conclusion, limitation, and recommendation.

³ In this research, IFMIS and BTMS are used interchangeably

CHAPTER II

Literature Review

This chapter presents the empirical studies on what we know so far about the factors that affect IFMIS implementation, the location, and the methodology used in studying IFMIS.

2.1 Determinant factors in IFMIS implementation

Many empirical studies have identified factors that influence the outcome of IFMIS implementation. Jared, Migiro, and Mutambara (2017) explored the IFMIS implementation by looking at certain theoretical paradigms involving success factors for IFMIS and how it applies in Migori County, Kenya. They fused various theories (Technology Acceptance Model (TAM); Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT), and Work Around Theory (WAT)) to pinpoint key factors, which include technical, organizational, environmental, cultural, and ethical behavior that contributes to the success or failure of IFMIS (Jared et al., 2017).⁴ **Table 1** below presents a summary of the various factors covered in their study:

Table 1. Summary of Factors on the Success and Failure of IFMIS		
Factors	Particulars	Source
Technological Factors	Covers basic system functionality: software and hardware	<i>Bonventure, 2015; Sussi, 2012; Hendriks, 2012; Cain, 2012; Chêne, 2010</i>
	Making simple and right technical choices greatly influences the success of IFMIS; contrary to this Proeller (2013) argues the that complexity of system has positive impact since it is more appreciated than simple ones	<i>Chene, 2010 Proeller, 2013</i>
	Platform used for interconnectivity of IFMIS (i.e. intranet, internet, web-based)	<i>Odunga, 2015</i>

⁴ First, the IDT suggests that IFMIS is an innovation perceived by users as new and influenced by five (5) factors: "Complexity, Compatibility, Trial-ability, Observability, and Relative Advantage" (Jared et al., 2017, p.39). IDT denotes the importance of communication channels in making decisions, the role of change agents, and the conduct of training. It gives importance to time to innovate the process, of the individuals, and the rate at which individuals adopt an innovation. More importantly, it covers the importance of the social system or the interrelated units working toward a common goal, like solving the problem of fragmented ICT systems. Secondly, the TAM covers the new system's perceived usefulness and ease of use. It tackles how users perceive the importance of the system to enhance job performance and how easily the technology can be used (Jared et al.,2017). Third, the WAT covers the idea that users perceive that IFMIS has certain obstacles when used. As such, WAT is how users carry out adaptation schemes to bypass or minimize the obstacle brought about by IFMIS.

Table 1. Summary of Factors on the Success and Failure of IFMIS		
Factors	Particulars	Source
	Lack of IT capacity, resistance due to complexity, technological challenges, and lack of IT staff	<i>Hendriks, 2012; Diamond & Khemani, 2005</i>
	Use of commercial off-the-shelf vs. locally developed software	<i>Dener et al., 2011</i>
	Power shortages and interruptions when using system servers	<i>Chene, 2010</i>
Organizational factors	Covers institutional processes and arrangements that govern the management of public funds	<i>Ameen & Ahmad, 2012; Chêne, 2010; Sussi, 2012</i>
	Organizational arrangements, the capacity of user skills, top management support, skilled laborer demanding more rewards, resistance due to trust and risk of use, and support for the use by middle managers	<i>Bwalya and Mutula, 2016; Lundu and Shale, 2015; Bonventure, 2015; Qwabe, 2014; Kiilu and Ngugi, 2014; Secretariat, 2013; Schniederjans and Yadav, 2013; Sussi, 2012; Peterson, 2002</i>
	Lack of coordination between the teams resulted in the IFMIS being incompatible with the system developed.	<i>Hove & Wynne, 2010</i>
Environmental factors	Availability of external skills, stakeholders, vendor support, competing software developers, software vendor trust, and ethical influences	<i>Zhao et al., 2015, Lundu & Shale, 2015, Bonventure, 2015, Qwabe, 2014, Secretariat, 2013, Cain, 2012, Elias, 2004, Healy & Perry, 2000, Richard, 2015</i>
Cultural and ethical factors	One's values or beliefs that distinguish the members of one group from another set of a group that influences user behavior in the technology adoption	<i>Zhao et al., 2015</i>
	IFMIS impacted negatively by corruption; moral principles that guide an individual or an organization into differentiating what is good from what is wrong	<i>Chowdhury, 2011</i>
	key results that the IFMIS system would provide is a reduction of corruption and fraud through the controls embedded within the system, but in practice, researchers have observed a lot of corruption cases associated with IFMIS in different government institutions and countries	<i>Bwalya and Mutula (2016), Qwabe (2014), Bwalya et al. (2014), Secretariat (2013), Prabir P. (2012), Hendriks (2012), Cain (2012); Lundu and Shale, 2015; Kahari et al., 2015</i>
Legal factors	The existence of a legal framework greatly impacts the management information system that a country would use in the management of public funds.	<i>Dener et al., 2011</i>

Source: Jared et al., 2017

The importance of political factors seems to be lacking in Jared et al. (2017) evaluation. While it is continuously debated, most authors suggest that a "firm political commitment and its underlying incentives are required" for the success of IFMIS (Combaz,2015, p.2). Diamond & Khemani (2006) noted that the consistent commitment of political leaders and high-ranking officials in management ensures IFMIS' success. Peterson (2006) countered that Ethiopia's IFMIS was successful despite only having mid-level management commitment. Joshi, Srivastava, and Nguyen (2020), in their FMIS study on Indonesia, Vietnam, Mongolia, and Timor-Leste, support the importance of political will, which they ranked as number one in their hierarchy of necessary factors for successful implementation of IFMIS. This hierarchy is summarized in **Figure 1** below:

Other empirical studies point to **technical factors** that affect the implementation of IFMIS. For one, whether to use an off-the-shelf (OTS) IFMIS or locally-developed IFMIS is a crucial factor in the successful outcome of IFMIS. Peterson (2006) argued that the main reason why IFMIS failed is the adoption of an OTS reform which "forces governments to adopt their systems making

reform that they would not otherwise make” (p.4). Other studies find that there must be true customization of an OTS IFMIS. Merely changing the configuration and creating customized reports is not true customization. Identifying important processes to be customized and possibly adapting COTS processes can save cost and time (Joshi et al., 2020).

Peterson (2006) presented a case study of Ethiopia as an example of IFMIS reform that worked. In his study, two frameworks: process innovation and process change, were distinguished in analyzing why IFMIS implementation succeeds/fails. Accordingly, **process innovation** involves reengineering, a comprehensive overhaul of procedures and organizations with information technology. This process usually uses conventional OTS IFMIS reform, which frequently exceeds the capacities of bureaucrats in developing countries. This process covers three (3) factors: **Scope, schedule, and budget**. As to scope, he highlighted the emerging experience from public sectors that "the greater the complexity and scale of the IT platform to support the financial systems, the greater the risk of failure or underperformance of the platform, and by extension the system as a whole”(Peterson, 2006, p.7). Peterson(2006) identified excessive coverage, prolonged development schedules, and budget constraints as reasons why in many developing countries experience, IFMIS failed or underperformed. On the other hand, **process change** is a less risky approach than process innovation and is aptly implementable in developing countries. It is an "incremental strategy driven by procedural reform and supported by information technology" (Peterson, 2006, p.3).

Technical discussions also looked at the essential functionalities of IFMIS as a system. Failure of IFMIS is primarily due to a lack of specification of the basic functionality at the outset (Chêne,2009). Peterson (2006) expounded on this issue by scrutinizing the typical features provided by Penrose (2005), detailed in **Figure 2**:

Figure 2. Features of a typical IFMIS

Based on the above figure, IFMIS can be classified into core and non-core functions. Core functions involve accounting and reporting, while non-core covers "budgeting, commitment control, cash management, and disbursement functions" (Peterson, 2006, p.9). However, this distinction is incomprehensive since the core function does not include all components for effective financial control. This problem stems from IFMIS being originally a private technology, and as such, it does not get the basics right for public sector financial management. Typically, IFMIS does not cover budget commitments to identify available cash for disbursement, which is a problem. Even if the necessary component is included, it does not prevent abuse and misuse of system users. As to its integrated function, IFMIS should be integrated by data management and modularity. Modular systems are made by having independent modules that can link data as user requirements evolve. The modularity of design is an essential feature of IFMIS that supports financial reform's sequential or gradual development. In Ethiopia, the custom IFMIS was flexible and easily customizable to run multiple versions of financial modules to consolidate data. Such a module design also requires running a manual system that can provide "a platform from which the user and the application developer can rapidly and cost-effectively evolve the system" (Peterson, 2006, p.13). According to Peterson, since it is impossible to automate everything, having a manual system supporting the modular process of an IFMIS approach is crucial.

Moreover, the management function supports the control, management, and planning function of IFMIS. The information functions translate financial data to information that IFMIS uses to provide financial reports. Finally, the system function provides the software and hardware requirements of IFMIS (Peterson, 2006).

True enough, the literature identified technical factors as among the crucial factors determining the success and failure of IFMIS (Combaz, 2015). However, there has been a misconception that PFM reform's outcome, like what IFMIS intends to solve, is primarily influenced by technical factors, such that realizing the goals is a matter of technical specification, skills, and appropriate mechanisms. Others argued that the **non-technical factors** of PFM reforms, in general, have a more crucial role in the success and failure of IFMIS (Diamond, 2013; Fritz et al.,2017). In the case of Ethiopia, Peterson (2006) found the following crucial non-technical factors: (a) institutional factors; (b) design of financial procedures; (c) effective project selection and management; and (d) reluctance to change. Combaz (2015) highlighted the importance of

institutional factors by arguing that implementing IFMIS too often resulted in failure and bred new corruption opportunities.

Jeong and Hwang (2021) highlighted South Korea's successful IFMIS⁵ implementation by considering the **business continuity plan** (BCP) as an utmost priority, particularly during the Covid pandemic. South Korea prioritized core functions of IFMIS like the supplemental budget for Covid and those required by law. From there, prioritization was made, and BCP was developed to ensure that the system operates under any circumstances. The BCP also gave due importance to safeguarding operational personnel and offsite user support to prevent halts in operation despite getting infected by Covid (Jeong & Hwang, 2021).

Another crucial category is staffing and staff capacities. Chêne (2009) pointed out that IFMIS needs capacitated staff throughout the government for IFMIS to be successful. Since there is low computer literacy in most developing countries and IFMIS is an advanced PFM reform, stakeholders (administrators, end-users) should undergo rigorous capacity building on its use.

For these factors to work favorably, Peterson (2010) pointed out that these should be aligned with **four drivers of public sector reform: context, ownership, purpose, and strategy (COPS)**. The idea of **context** requires considering the country's political, economic, and social condition, existing structures' organizational and bureaucratic cultures, and the necessary conditions for implementing reform, whether there is trust, need, or urgency to institute changes. Diamonds (2013) stressed the importance of underlying political, administrative, and cultural context, institutions' role, and political and managerial leadership in successfully implementing reforms. Secondly, as Peterson (2010) observed, reforms work depending on who owns the process. **Ownership** tackles whether reforms are government-led or donor-led. The former involves the strong involvement of the administration and domestic decision-makers. At the same time, the latter concerns the heavy influence of donor institutions in the PFM reform of a particular country. Ownership also covers the role of the agents in the process, whether there is a high technical capacity of managers and civil servants, high centralization of power (Lawson et al., 2012), and how reforms are limited based on whether agents are concentrated or distributed (Andrews, 2014).

⁵ South Korea's successful pandemic response was largely due to its Digital Budget and Accounting System, dBrain. "[...]through the dBrain, the Korean government organizes, executes, and accounts for a 500 trillion Korean won budget and manages its national assets...In short, if dBrain stops, all aspects of the Korean government's financial policy stop" (Jeong & Hwang, 2021,p.584).

The third driver of PFM reform is the **purpose**. Whether the goal as put forward by Peterson (2010) is to implement international best practices (advance reforms) or to have a financial plateau (basic reforms), which means getting the basics right as Schick (1998) earlier suggested or having small wins as elaborated by Peterson (2010). IFMIS was seen as an advanced international best practice type of reform (Peterson,2010) and usually takes off-the-shelf platforms, often resulting in failures. Lastly, **strategy** as a driver of reform suggests recognizing existing systems, improving them if needed, and sustaining or changing them if necessary.

2.3 Empirical studies on IFMIS based on location and methodology

Most empirical studies on IFMIS for developing countries are located in Africa. Muwema and Phiri (2020) tackled the impact of IFMIS on the procurement process in the case of Zambia. They used a descriptive survey among 75 respondents from the Ministry of Finance and found a significant negative relationship between IFMIS and transparency, reducing financial leakages and efficiency. Lundu and Shale (2015) covered the effect of IFMIS on the supply chain management performance in the devolved governments in Nairobi, Kenya using a quantitative approach, with 400 government employees purposively sampled. Also, in Kenya, Kahari et al. (2015) underscored a strong correlation between staff resistance and IFMIS implementation as a result of a survey among 70 government employees. Karanja and Nganga (2014) covered Kenya and analyzed the factors influencing IFMIS using a descriptive quantitative design. They highlighted funding as the main factor that influenced IFMIS implementation. Tetteh et al. (2021), using a case study in Ghana's Controller and Accountant General's Department, discovered that IFMIS reform was due to external pressure from the WB and internal stakeholders who were dissatisfied with previous reforms. They also found that for it to be successful, there must be a commitment from internal stakeholders and capacity building to improve required skills. Laizer and Suomi (2017) conducted an IFMIS evaluation in Tanzania using purposive sampling of various local authorities. They found that the 18 years of IFMIS implementation is bogged down by systems interoperability, proliferation, and lack of IFMIS policies and standards.

Quarm et al. (2020) studied the effects of IFMIS platforms given the Covid-19 pandemic, using Ghana as the empirical example. They conducted cross-sectional research through purposive sampling with 200 respondents. Their main findings support the importance of IFMIS in effective cash management. Interestingly, the study identified the key end-users of IFMIS as follows: budget officers, accountants, procurement officers, store officers, internal auditors, treasury

officers, administrators and HR managers, spending officers, vote controllers, and external auditors (Quarm et al. 2020).

The literature suggests how World Bank (WB) seems to be the major moving force for IFMIS. Mostly in Africa, WB has financed 151 projects in 84 countries.⁶ Since 1984 WB suggested a step-by-step approach for designing and implementing IFMIS: (1): “identify the government's needs for PFM reform first (What? Why?); develop customized solutions (How? Where? When?) and strengthen institutional capacity to manage IFMIS activities effectively (Who?).” (Dener, Watkins & Dorotinsky, 2011, as cited in Combaz, 2015, p.7).

The scarce case studies on IFMIS in the Southeast Asian region are quite noticeable. One is the study of PEMNA through Joshi et al. (2020) which covered Indonesia, Vietnam, Mongolia, and Timor-Leste conducted through survey and semi-structured questionnaires which identified various factors influencing IFMIS and lessons learned. Berman (2016), in his book on public administration in Southeast Asia, highlighted the importance of familial traditions of close-knit relationships and kinship in public administration, which is enhanced by the overlapping functions in the Philippine bureaucracy (Brillantes & Lorenzo, 2021). Jeong and Hwang (2021) presented South Korea's IFMIS (dBrain), focusing on its importance in the Covid-19 response of the country.

Despite the importance of institutional factors and staff resistance, it was observed that there is an absence of thorough empirical studies which look at the comparison of different groups such as distributed and concentrated agents and how their perception influences the outcome of IFMIS. While Andrews (2010, 2014) initiated this topic and assessed externally-supported PFM reforms, it has never been replicated/tested in another setting. More on this study are discussed in the theoretical framework (Chapter 3).

2.4 Literature gap

Given the above literature review, the researcher finds merit in conducting a mixed method case study, focusing on the Philippines' IFMIS implementation and evaluating whether the different perceptions of government agents affect the outcome of an externally-supported PFM reform.

⁶ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/governance/brief/financial-management-information-systems-fmis>

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the theoretical framework and research methodology that lays the groundwork for the researcher to assess the perceptions of agents (concentrated and distributed) in implementing IFMIS in the Philippines. Further, it provides the operational framework that serves as basis for the analysis of the study's findings.

3.1 Declaration of positionality

At the outset, it must be noted that the researcher is a post-positivist with an underlying notion that the dynamics of PFM reforms can be understood by an eclectic approach such that theories can be falsified and theoretical design can be continuously revised or enhanced. Post-positivism is also interpretive in tone, concentrating on understanding social phenomena as opposed to positivists' absolutist goal of identifying causality or explanation using a scientific method (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). This permissible stance of post-positivism strongly resonates with my worldview as a political scientist and civil servant.⁷ Levy and Fukuyama (2010) provided development strategies to understand social phenomena through multidimensional frameworks that attempt to explain developmental issues. The researcher argues that this approach is also what Andrews (2014) performed that served as the main reference for this study.

Moreover, the realist ontology of post-positivism acknowledges independent social actors and the dynamics among other actors and various perceptions. The theory of Andrews earlier discussed is viewed as an example of a post-positivist model of empirical research which resonates with the contemporary concept of evidence-based practice (Mertens, 2015) as "[r]esearch generates the rules of practice that practitioners are to follow" (Willis, 2007, p.78).

The researcher believes that the world (social phenomena) cannot be seen objectively as a positivist would claim since humans have inherent cognitive biases. Thus, social facts/findings are value-laden, and our approaches to understanding them are theory-laden (Miller, 2005). My role as a researcher is to be aware of my biases and limitations and situate myself as far as possible from the research participants to approximate objectivity. Nevertheless, as a researcher, the aim is to be

⁷ The researcher has been working for the DBM for the last ten years.

rigorous to arrive at a possible objective outcome using various methods that highlight the internal and external validity of data complemented by an in-depth analysis using mixed methods (Kanbur & Shaffer, 2007). The researcher observed the following theoretical and methodological underpinnings for answering the research questions of this study.

3.2 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This research is anchored on the institutional change theory, which looks at PFM reforms as institutional change. IFMIS is deemed an institutional change because it affects the work processes and setup of public financial management (Chêne, 2009). The following types of institutional mechanisms influence the behavior of agents: (1) **regulative mechanisms** (laws); (2) **normative mechanisms** (values, what is acceptable or appropriate to agents); and (3) **cultural-cognitive mechanisms** (religion, nationality, language) that create rule-like frames which agents are inclined to observe (Andrews, 2014; Alesina & Perotti, 1999, Scott, 2008; Ostrom, 2008). These mechanisms are grouped by Scott (2008) as elements, whether formal or informal, which establish rules that shape agents' thinking and behaviors.

Andrews likened this theory to the iceberg metaphor (**Figure 3**), whereby institutions become incumbent rules and eventually turn very difficult to change over time.

Figure 3. Institutional Structures as Icebergs (Andrews, 2014)

However, Andrews (2014) argues that despite institutional structures becoming seemingly irreversible, particularly when agents have to invest in them over a long time, there are still **conditions that influence institutions to change**, as follows:

1. **There must be disruption** (i.e., global financial crises, pandemics, worrying concerns over corruption in the workplace, and emerging problems) that cause agents to question the capacity of incumbent structures to resolve the above situations. In these circumstances, agents are confronted by loopholes and weaknesses of pre-existing rules and begin to search for alternatives, creating windows of opportunity for reform.
2. **Agents believe that incumbent rules have lost legitimacy.** In such cases, agents will be open to reform ideas. Otherwise, changes to the rules are not welcome because they are more familiar and comfortable with the status quo.
3. **Agents believe that reform alternatives are legitimate and practical.** They will be more open to alternatives that they have seen or personally experienced in the workplace, which are politically acceptable, and complementary to the necessary skills to adopt alternative reforms and shape them to their local context.
4. **Agents are engaged in making such change happen.** The idea is to involve those who will implement the reforms, and they should be made part of the design and process development. The effect is process ownership which makes them more likely to support reforms and will help foster the adoption in the local context. Otherwise, they will not actively support new mechanisms. As such, one could expect that it will not be adapted in the local context, making it hard to be politically and practically possible (Andrews,2014).

Andrews (2014) emphasizes that the extent of institutional change brought about by reform in any context depends on the above conditions. Positively meeting such conditions, one can expect high success rates, but when not, particularly in the case of distributed agents, limited reform should be expected.

Under the above theory, four hypotheses considering institutional factors and reform conditions were tested:

“H1: Distributed agents will limit reforms because they are less likely than concentrated agents to agree that the context is disrupted by PFM-specific problems” (p.11).

Andrews (2014) postulated that distributed agents are less concerned with specific PFM problems that usually pave the way for PFM reform. They are more preoccupied with the hosts of problems encountered in their pursuit of particular agency mandates. Contrarily, the concentrated agents are routinely focused on PFM problems because of their oversight roles. They directly engage with international organizations like WB and IMF, strengthening their niche on PFM problems. This is not to say that distributed agents do not encounter PFM problems or are less aware of PFM problems that need fixing. Andrews argued that such a condition is less likely to become the main concern that receives attention to foster change.

“H2: Distributed agents will limit reforms because they are less likely than the concentrated agents to agree that the incumbent PFM rules of the game (promoting local resource control and allowing political influence) have lost legitimacy” (p.12).

Andrews argued that PFM reforms commonly replace informal systems with more formal ones and usually intend to centralize PFM processes like hiring and collecting revenues into TSA managed at the central level. PFM reforms also depoliticize budgeting through efficient planning and multi-year budgeting. His hypothesis suggests that distributed agents may consider these new mechanisms inappropriate and view incumbent rules as more legitimate. This applies when incumbent systems allow distributed agents to have more control over their resources, to hire locally, collect revenues, and keep them in their bank accounts. Moreover, distributed agents see their day-to-day transactions as more political interactions. They see that depoliticizing the budget process through mainly technical PFM processes is unacceptable (Andrews, 2014).

“H3: Distributed agents will limit reforms because they are less likely than concentrated agents to consider PFM reform alternatives as legitimate and practical” (p.13).

Andrews (2014) suggested that distributed agents may be less inclined to see introduced reforms as more legitimate than existing systems simply because they have no reference points to make sense of such ideas. Contrarily, concentrated agents have more experience in study visits about a particular reform which is usually based on an international best practice since they mostly deal with external donors. However, distributed agents are assumed to be more attuned to the realities on the ground. As such, they may see existing legal and system arrangements as hindrances to the full implementation of reform. They may also be less optimistic than concentrated agents on the capacities of implementors and willingness to implement PFM reforms and the dynamics between the innovation and political interests (Andrews, 2014).

“H4: Distributed agents will limit reforms because they are less likely to be engaged in PFM reform design than concentrated agents.” (p.13).

Andrews observed that most PFM reforms are designed by a small group of staff in PFM oversight agencies like the Ministry of Finance in consultation with external donors and experts. PFM designs are usually OTS from developed countries and rarely engage distributed agents. As such, contributions of distributed agents are seldomly included in the design. They are seen as "change targets" instead of change partners or "change agents" (p.13). Therefore, Andrews postulates that failure to engage them compromises ownership and support, resulting in a limited reform.

3.3 Operational Framework

This section clarifies how we translated the above theory’s hypotheses and concepts to focus on the Philippines’ IFMIS/BTMS as a particular externally-supported reform. The details of the Philippine case are presented further in Chapter 4. The following discussion presents the variables included and justified additional improvements made in Andrews's study based on existing literature and the Philippine context.

For this purpose, the independent variable is the agents involved (concentrated and distributed). In the case of Andrews, concentrated agents are limited to those working in the Ministry of Finance.

However, in this study, the definition is expanded by including government employees from the PFM Committee identified under EO No. 55, composed of the DBM, DOF, BTr, and COA. While Andrews' study only covers budgeters, accountants, and auditors for the distributed agents, this research included other employees identified in Quarms (2020), i.e., procurement officers, treasury officers, administrators and HR managers, spending officers, but excluded vote controllers and external auditors.

The explanatory or dependent variables are the different perceptions of IFMIS by those groups based on the factors (reform conditions) obtained from existing literature. These are organized under the four hypotheses discussed above and further explained in **Table 2** below:

Table 2. Dependent Variables

Hypotheses	Explanatory variables	Justification	Source
H1:	Reform condition: context is disrupted by a problem		
Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than concentrated agents to agree that the context is disrupted by PFM-specific problems;	(1) Resources (manpower, time, funds) are not maximized in the current/existing system;	This variable represents the emerging problems that cause agents to question the capacity of incumbent structures to resolve the above situations.	Andrews (2014)
	(2) Current/existing financial management and reporting systems are not integrated (i.e. systems are interlinked, interoperable, interfaced)	This highlights a specific PFM/IFMIS-related problem.	Stanforth (2016)
	(3) The new normal brought about by the COVID pandemic requires a more integrated (interlinked,	This variable is added to specifically meet the condition in Andrews (2014) that there must be a disruption in the form of the pandemic.	Quarm et al. (2020)

Hypotheses	Explanatory variables	Justification	Source
	interoperable, interfaced) IT systems		
	(4) Maintaining the current/existing system already ensures proper allocation of financial resources	This is to test which group prefers more or less the status quo as they do not see a problem in the allocation of resources.	Quarm et al. (2020)
	(5) Maintaining the current/existing system may lead to possible corruption issues	Identified criteria of Andrews that test whether the status quo is disrupted by a problem of corruption.	Andrews (2014)
H2:	Incumbents/Rules are weakened, agents reject incumbent logic		
Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than the concentrated agents to agree that the incumbent PFM rules have lost legitimacy;	(1) Hiring should be centralized, not delegated to local/lower units (i.e regional heads/officers, provincial, municipal offices)	This tests the notion that centralized hiring systems are favored by concentrated agents while decentralized hiring, leaving the discretion to local officials is favored by distributed agents.	Andrews (2014)
	(2) Authority to manage revenue collections should be centralized, not delegated to local/lower units (i.e regional heads/officers, provincial, municipal offices)	This tests the assumption that distributed agents prefer holding the collected revenues to themselves as against concentrated agents based on PFM reform trends and prefer it to be centrally managed.	Andrews (2014)
	(3) The budget process is more technical than political	This tests the assumption that the budget process is technical as per the thinking of many PFM reforms while it is political based on thinking in many incumbent systems.	Andrews (2014)

Hypotheses	Explanatory variables	Justification	Source
H3:	IFMIS is seen as a legitimate and a viable alternative		
Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than concentrated agents to consider IFMIS as a legitimate and practical reform alternative;	(1) Implementing agencies/units tend to resist the application of IFMIS/BTMS	This tests whether distributed agents resist IFMIS because they do not have a reference point to check its advantage over existing systems. Usually, concentrated agents are recipients of field visits and information on the advantages of a reform. Hence, they appreciate more the benefits of the externally sponsored PFM reforms	Andrews (2014)
	(2) IFMIS, or its scaled-down version (BTMS) is the right reform solution	This statement tests which group prefers IFMIS/BTMS as a legitimate alternative.	Andrews (2014)
	(3) Existing systems/procedures should be improved (improve what exists rather than a comprehensive replacement)	This statement is an additional item in line with the assumption that IFMIS is either a process innovation or process change. If respondents agree that it should be improved, then the preferred alternative should be an incremental change instead of complete overhaul like what OTS IFMIS usually offers	Peterson (2006)
	(4) Existing systems/procedures should be replaced (comprehensive change of procedures and	This statement intends to test preference of respondents on having process innovation vs process change which validates perception on	Peterson (2006)

Hypotheses	Explanatory variables	Justification	Source
H3: Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than concentrated agents to consider IFMIS as a legitimate and practical reform alternative;	processes driven by information technology)	whether IFMIS is appropriately designed.	
	(5) Systems developed in-house (locally, based on existing systems upgrade) work better than commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) platforms (ready-made available for purchase in commercial market)	This is also an additional statement that assess the preference of agents on IFMIS, whether OTS or custom-built. This supports the assumption on whether IFMIS, as currently designed, is the right reform solution.	Peterson (2006, 2010)
	(6) Existing legal arrangements (Executive Order No.55, s.2011) is sufficient for the effective implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	This statement is the contextualized assumption on whether extant legal system adds to skepticism of distributed agents on IFMIS as a viable reform.	Andrews (2014)
	(7) There is a need for institutionalization of BTMS and IFMIS-related reforms through legislative enactment	This statement validates item 6 because EO 55 is an executive issuance, item 7 assess the preference of agents on having a law to support IFMIS for it to be more viable as reform.	Jeong & Hwang, (2021)
	(8) Current/existing systems arrangements (technical, non-technical capacities, and business processes) prevents the successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	This statement tests the viability of IFMIS given the extant system characteristics. If the agents agree on this, then they view as a limitation casting doubt on the viability of reform.	Andrews (2014)
(9) The current/existing capacities of administrators (i.e. approver, reviewer,	If agents believe that the capacities of administrators are insufficient, this challenges the	Andrews (2014)	

Hypotheses	Explanatory variables	Justification	Source
H3: Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success	heads of agencies, bureaus, divisions) to implement IFMIS/BTMS are insufficient	viability of IFMIS. Distributed agents are expected to agree more on this item than the concentrated agents to support H3.	
because they are less likely than concentrated agents to consider IFMIS as a legitimate and practical reform alternative;	(10) The current level of political will of administrators (i.e. approver, reviewer, heads of agencies, bureaus, divisions) prevents higher chances of IFMIS/BTMS' successful implementation	If agents perceive that political will is a limitation, then it will cast doubts among distributed agents that IFMIS will be pushed better towards other priority agenda.	Andrews (2014)
	(11) The political environment is favorable to the successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	If the agents agree with this statement, then political concerns are not a limitation. Distributed agents are assumed to be less likely than concentrated agents to see that the current political environment makes IFMIS a viable reform.	Andrews (2014)
H4: Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success	Agents are engaged behind reforms		
because they are less likely to be engaged in	(1) Level of involvement in the IFMIS/BTMS reform design	These statements assess the engagement of agents. It is assumed that distributed agents	Andrews (2014)
	(2) Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were engaged enough in	are not engaged in the initial design phase of the reform. This will be more apparent if the IFMIS platform used is a COTS. Thus, when they were	Andrews (2014)

Hypotheses	Explanatory variables	Justification	Source
H4: Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely to be engaged in IFMIS design than concentrated agents	designing the system for IFMIS/BTMS	not made part during the design stage, H4 predicts that failure to engage them compromises ownership and support and results in a limited reform.	Andrews (2014)
	(3) Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were not given enough opportunity to practice with and adapt the IFMIS/BTMS to context (agency needs, capacity constraints)		
	(4) Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were given time to implement the proposed reform like BTMS		Andrews (2014)
	(5) Were there enough capacity-building / training opportunities to use IFMIS/BTMS?	This question is asked to further validate H4 and evaluate the factor on the capacity building since most agents in developing countries are assumed to lack necessary training on IT-related reforms. Thus, this requirement makes capacity building an essential factor in the success of IFMIS/BTMS.	Chene (2009)

3.4 Research Design

This action research employs a mixed-method case study to test the above hypotheses and answer the research questions. Action research seeks to bring together theory and practice, action and reflection, in pursuit of practical solutions to issues of concern (Wicks et al., 2008). Andrews (2014) argues that applied action research is the ideal method within reform processes, "focused on examining how different groups actually think and engage with real reforms" (p.22). Moreover, "a mixed-methods case study design is a type of mixed methods study in which the quantitative and qualitative data collection, results, and integration are used to provide in-depth evidence for a case(s)" (Cresswell & Plano Clarke, 2018, p.116). Mixed methods in the development sector provide credibility in answering complex research questions, allowing for triangulation, complementarity, and expansion to reach justifiable conclusions (Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). This paper follows an exploratory sequential design as a form of mixed methods case study, presented in **Figure 4**, to describe a phenomenon in its real-world context (Yin, 2014).

Figure 4. Exploratory sequential Mixed Methods Case Study

Source: Cook and Kamalodeen, 2019, slide 22

3.5 Methodology

To test the above hypotheses and follow the mixed method case study approach, the researcher performed document analyses of academic and grey literature to generate key codes and develop a survey instrument to gather primary data. This study gathered quantitative cross-sectional data to reach many respondents rapidly. Thematic analysis on key informant interviews and open-ended questionnaires were also conducted to triangulate survey results and to have a deeper understanding of the differences in perception, thereby pinpointing factors for IFMIS success.

3.6 Sampling strategy

This research utilizes a non-probability sampling approach, strategically targeting specific respondents so that those sampled are relevant to the research questions (Bryman, 2012). As earlier identified, the sample selection is all government personnel from concentrated and distributed agencies. Details are provided in Chapter 4.

3.7 Data collection tools and procedures

Based on the research question, we need to assess the difference in perception of two groups and evaluate whether this will affect the outcome of the reform. As such, we coiled a questionnaire composed of the following: six (6) fact-finding questions on the demographic profile of the respondents, seven (7) fact-finding questions on awareness and experience on IFMIS, and 22 5-pt Likert scale questions that assess agreements on statements related to reform conditions that validate how the two groups' perception in IFMIS implementation varies with the four hypotheses established. A copy of the survey is provided in **Appendix 1a**.

The questionnaire was piloted in one budget operations bureau of the DBM (concentrated agents) and a select line/implementing agency (distributed agents) in the first week of July 2022. The pilot testing helped minimize order effects and response biases by clarifying vague questions and arranging them accordingly. The researcher secured approval from the DBM head to conduct the survey with the respondents (**Appendix 1** - approval to conduct survey). The final survey was launched via google form from July 12, 2022, to July 27, 2022, among the target population. The respondents were assured confidentiality to minimize risk of social response bias.

Also, several interviews from concentrated and distributed agencies were conducted to gain first-hand information on these agents' perspectives and experiences. The interviews were conducted using a semi-structured approach via Facebook messenger and Google Meet. The interviewees were purposively sampled based on the concentrated and distributed group categories.

The researcher interviewed key informants to explore the historical background and challenges encountered, validate survey results, and identify the next steps for implementing IFMIS/BTMS. Select respondent-informants represented the distributed agents and expounded survey results for completeness and triangulation (see **Appendix 2** for the interview questions). The researcher

executed a follow-up survey via email and informal interviews with the survey respondents to validate their responses and dig deeper into the “neutral” answers from the survey (**Appendix 3 – Follow-up survey**).

3.8 Methods of data analysis

The quantitative data aims to test whether statistical significance exists in the different perceptions between concentrated and distributed agents. This paper resorts to the descriptive and inferential analysis of statistical data obtained from the questionnaire to establish group distinctions. Frequency tables and percentages are presented for the demographic profiles.

Mean, median, t-test, and Mann-Whitney U-test are presented for the Likert scales data. While Likert scales are always an ordinal variable, if ranges can be ascertained like the consistent 1 to 5 measure of a Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," then it can be classified as an interval variable (Bryman,2012). In this regard, the Likert scale questions are grouped per hypothesis, and the results are averaged to create a continuous variable. As such, the mean is an applicable measure of central tendency, and parametric analysis like t-tests may provide inferential statistics on the average. However, non-parametric tests are mainly employed, such as the Mann-Whitney U test⁸ given majority of variables are not normally distributed and to compare two groups purposively sampled (de Winter & Dodou, 2010). Various statistical tools such as Microsoft Excel and STATA are used.

For the qualitative data from open-ended questionnaires and interviews, thematic analyses were employed on the transcriptions and documents using NVivo to assess patterns, trends, and relationships, deepen understanding of the answers to the research questions, and validate findings from the questionnaires.

⁸ used to compare differences between two independent groups when the dependent variable is either ordinal or continuous but not normally distributed (<https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/mann-whitney-u-test-using-spss-statistics.php>)

3.9 Reliability and Validity test

Bryman (2012) defines reliability as fundamentally concerning "issues of consistency of measurement" (p.168). For this research, dependability is assessed primarily through internal reliability. It measures whether the respondent's score is consistent with his scores on another indicator. The internal reliability test applies to multiple-indicator measures used by this research. Cronbach's alpha, the most commonly used test for internal reliability (Bryman, 2012), displayed our questionnaire's Cronbach's score at 0.75 (details in **Appendix 4**), which suggest a high level of acceptability for internal consistency, i.e., those test items are interrelated among associated concepts (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Since this research intended to test a theory, construct validity is also an apt measure. It is a measure based on deducing hypotheses from a theory relevant to a particular topic (Bryman, 2012). The consistency of items/indicators is well founded based on the following: (a) four hypotheses on how distributed end-users often limit reform success by Andrews, (b) the acceptable Cronbach's Alpha, and (3) the positive feedback on the pre-survey and the follow-up interviews with respondents.

3.10 Ethical consideration

In this study, the researcher observed the ethical code of conduct and principles for research at the University of Antwerp. Details are provided in **Appendix 5**.

CHAPTER IV

The Philippines' IFMIS Reform Experience

This chapter presents the chosen locale of the study, target population, and a brief history of the Philippines' IFMIS and implementation challenges.

4.1 Locale of the study and target population

This research takes the case of the Philippines' experience with IFMIS implementation. For its target population, this research covers the following **concentrated agents**: PFM Committee established under EO No. 55, promulgated in 2011, to lead the development of an IFMIS for the government and to implement a PFM reforms roadmap (EO 55, 2011)⁹:

1. **Department of Budget and Management (DBM)** – mandated to promote the sound, efficient, and effective management and utilization of government resources (i.e., technological, workforce, physical and financial).¹⁰ The DBM is the main proponent of the BTMS.
2. **Department of Finance - Bureau of the Treasury (DOF - BTr)** – mandated to manage the cash resources of the National Government, maintain books of accounts of cash transactions, to formulate operational guidelines for fiscal and financial policies, among others provided under the law.¹¹ The BTr is the main administrator of the TSA, an important component of the IFMIS.

Distributed agents from the Finance and Accounting Office, Cash Department, Budget Office; Purchasing/Procurement Office, General Services Department, and - Administrative Offices of national government agencies who attended the FY 2022/23 budget forum (details are provided in **Appendix 6**).

4.2 Genesis of IFMIS implementation in the Philippines

The idea of IFMIS has been around the country for decades, but its actual development has slowly progressed. As early as 1998, "initial phase of the development of an IFMIS has begun with the development of a Budget Execution and Tracking (BEAT) system" with the assistance of WB

⁹ for lack of available respondents, the COA was eventually excluded as participants.

¹⁰ <https://www.dbm.gov.ph/index.php/about-us/mandate>

¹¹ https://www.treasury.gov.ph/?page_id=44465

(Diokno,1999, p.141). However, the main collective efforts started in May 2009. The DBM, DOF, and COA met at a PFM reform workshop to discuss the results of the diagnostic assessment of the PEFA for the Philippines PFM system. Main issue and realization were to have an integrated system for PFM oversight agencies to have an effective system for recording, reporting, and analyzing budget processes and financial information. Here, an informal group of individuals from the said agencies and other line agencies was created to pursue the issues discovered at the workshop.¹²

In January 2010, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed, establishing a formal group to cooperate on the development of the IFMIS. In February 2010, another workshop defined the PFM reform strategies and roadmap. Later on, this group became the GIFMIS committee. While there was a change in administration in July 2010, the group benefitted from the technical assistance of WB and PFM expert Cem Dener. In November 2010, heads of COA, DBM, and DOF affirmed commitment to the development of IFMIS in the Philippines.¹³

By 2011, the GIFMIS committee imbued its resources (manpower, time, and funds) in crafting measures to simplify data sharing, treasure accounts, budget execution, and the operationalization of IFMIS as part of the PFM reform roadmap (pfm.gov.ph). EO 55, s. 2011 mandated the PFM committee (DBM, DOF/BTR, COA, formerly GIFMIS committee) to proceed with the development of IFMIS.¹⁴

Since then, the approval of the IFMIS was tremendously sought by the PFM committee through the DBM. In February 2014, the DBM secured an audience with the cabinet ministers and the President, asking for his approval with the following justifications:

1. GIFMIS standardizes the processes across the budget cycle, defines and enforces user authorities, and centralizes reporting functionalities.
2. GIFMIS aims to consolidate fiscal information for oversight and implementing agencies to facilitate macroeconomic, monetary, and fiscal policy decision-making. The whole government will have access to real-time information.

¹² <https://pfm.gov.ph/pfm-reform-roadmap/genesis-of-the-pfm-reform-roadmap/>

¹³ <https://pfm.gov.ph/pfm-reform-roadmap/genesis-of-the-pfm-reform-roadmap/>

¹⁴ <https://www.treasury.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Executive-Order-No.-55.pdf>

3. GIFMIS ensures comprehensive reports on the actual expenditure of government agencies, and using the UACS, will pave the way for better monitoring of programs and projects.
4. The cash management and the accounts receivable modules of GIFMIS will enhance the efficiency of revenue collection and management.
5. GIFMIS will help in the irreversibility of PFM reforms.
6. GIFMIS eliminates the cost of developing, operating, and maintaining multiple disparate IT systems. About 69 individual IT-based PFM systems are not integrated and interoperable.
7. GIFMIS is expected to generate large interest savings due to the centralization of government balances, monitoring the availability of cash, and avoiding unnecessary idle cash balances.
8. Timely payments can be made from 3 to 4 weeks to 1 to 3 days of processing (DBM, 2014).

The IFMIS approval process passed through the scrutiny of the NEDA-Investment Coordination Committee – Cabinet Committee in 2014, where the PFM committee reiterated the value of IFMIS for tracking financial and physical performance information and improving capacities in PFM (DBM, 2014a).

The original design of the government IFMIS involves four (4) phases:

1. **Business process readiness.** Certain business processes have to be set in place, like establishing TSA, developing UACS, harmonizing budgetary and accounting reporting, mapping business processes, aligning current processes to a computerized accounting system, and auditing based on international standards.
2. **IT configuration** phase where system integrator will be hired to configure IT system based on governments' PFM business processes and policies.
3. **Pilot testing** where IFMIS will be implemented in oversight agencies (DBM, DOF, COA, and BTr) and selected revenue agencies (BIR, BOC) and spending agencies (DPWH).
4. **Roll-out** phase (DBM, 2014a).

The prerequisite reforms like the TSA had already been established in 2013, and the UACS was implemented in 2014. Budget execution reports were initially harmonized, and various accounting and auditing standards were reviewed and aligned with international standards.

The indicative budget for IFMIS was pegged at Php2.1 billion or USD40.384 million (at Php52 exchange rate to USD1). The government has pursued an action plan for PFM reform mandated by EO 55, and a top achievement has been the launch of the BTMS.

4.3 Budget and Treasury Management System (BTMS)

The development of BTMS started in 2014 (DBM, 2014), since the GIFMIS failed to get the green light. BTMS used a commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) solution purchased in 2015 for the execution and accountability phases of the PFM cycle. "BTMS acts as an enabler of the PFM reform program, which seeks to strengthen, standardize and automate the operational systems of the Philippine government" (Magsino,2018, slide 10). Like envisioned IFMIS, it hopes to facilitate efficient collection and organization of financial transactions through a centralized database that will allow further real-time information transparency. The difference is that BTMS focused on the modular implementation of budget execution and accountability.

It was operational in 2018 with the following modules: Budget Management, Commitments Management/Budget Utilization, and Cash and Treasury Management.¹⁵ However, the Budget Management module and the Treasury Management modules, mainly designed for the oversight functions of the DBM and the BTr, respectively, were not fully rolled out. The BTMS functional configuration is provided in **Figure 5**:

Figure 5. BTMS Functional Configuration

BTMS Functional Configuration

Source: 2019/20 KSP Policy Consultation Report

¹⁵ <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/3fcff7a44bd530a0413e23245ace2f03-0350012021/related/2021-IFMIS-CBP-Virtual-Workshop-Report-final.pdf>

Based on the above figure, the BTMS operates on a framework that captures all financial transactions at source and in near real-time. With this capability, transactions are mapped from the cradle to the grave, i.e., from purchase to payment. As of now, BTMS supports the existing disbursement frameworks, i.e., MDS and TSA, thus enabling the adoption of payment and cash management reforms. The BTMS Budget Utilization (BU) Module allows the recording of expenditure payments. After recording in the forms and books of original entries, the BTMS generates comprehensive financial reports at the consolidated government-wide (aggregated) and agency levels.¹⁶

After its pilot implementation in 2018 with the DBM, BTr, DPWH, and DTI, the adoption and use of BTMS were mandated for budget utilization of agencies in 2019. Section 5 of DBM Circular Letter 2019-4 provides that BTMS shall be used to execute expenditures per the budget law (General Appropriations Act)¹⁷. BTMS use was then expanded to 13 more agencies, including top spending agencies (DSWD, DepEd, DND)¹⁸.

“The BTMS development cost is around \$10M, licensing cost (10,000 concurrent users) is \$11M, and three-year product support cost is \$5M (2018-2020). As of 2020, the total costs amount to around \$32M (P1,531,614,579), which includes the earlier provided amounts, as well as other BTMS related costs on rollout, change management, infrastructure application upgrades and other overhead expenses” (KPFIS, 2021, p.13).

The BTMS was among the beneficiaries of an IBRD Reimbursable Advisory Service (RAS)¹⁹ in 2018-2019, thus an externally-supported PFM reform in line with Andrews’ study (World Bank Report No. 143605-PH).

¹⁶ <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/3fcff7a44bd530a0413e23245ace2f03-0350012021/related/2021-IFMIS-CBP-Virtual-Workshop-Report-final.pdf>

¹⁷ <https://www.dbm.gov.ph/index.php/issuances/dbm-issuances/circular-letters/231-latest-issuances/circular-letter/circular-letter-2019/1335-circular-letter-no-2019-4>

¹⁸ <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/3fcff7a44bd530a0413e23245ace2f03-0350012021/related/2021-IFMIS-CBP-Workshop-Philippines.pdf>

¹⁹ “RAS is an instrument developed to deliver advisory services to eligible clients requiring services that the Bank's country program cannot fully fund” <https://www.worldbank.org/en/region/eca/brief/reimbursable-advisory-services>

4.4 The challenges encountered

According to Aromin (2021)²⁰ the Philippines IFMIS, through BTMS, suffered the following challenges:

1. Reform fatigue which caused resistance to implementation by national government agencies;
2. Issue of change management for the integration of BTMS in business processes;
3. Complexities of implementing a COTS;
4. Operational issues in workflow and user management, and data migration;
5. Delays in contract management; and
6. Issue of establishing effective and responsive process monitoring controls (Aromin, 2021)

Thus, in 2021, the BTMS suffered another disapproval. This time, the DBM Bids and Awards Committee (BAC) recommended the award of the contract on the BTMS project with FreeBalance. However, the BAC resolution received disapproval from DBM Secretary Wendel Avisado, citing the pandemic and updates on the e-NGAs (v2.1) of COA and the National Government Collection and Disbursement System (NGCDS) of the BTr.²¹ The DBM Secretary as the PFM Principal, issued on July 26, 2021, Advisory No. 2021-08, suspending the use, rollout, and further development of the BTMS effective August 1, 2021.

²⁰ Interview in the KPFIS 2021 Capacity Building Program.
<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/3fcff7a44bd530a0413e23245ace2f03-0350012021/related/2021-IFMIS-CBP-Virtual-Workshop-Report-final.pdf>

²¹ Per key informant interview, August 5, 2022

CHAPTER V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the study's main findings, subdivided into the following sections: Demographic profile of the respondents (Section 5.1), descriptive statistics (Section 5.2), and results of hypotheses testing (Section 5.3). The demographic data helps us understand the profile of our respondents. The descriptive statistics populate our methodology with actual data, while the validation of hypotheses through statistical tests assesses groups' differences supported by qualitative interviews for deeper analysis.

5.1 Demographic profile

The demographic profile of 267 respondents is shown in **Table 3** below.

		Type of Agent							
		Concentrated			Distributed			Total	
		n	%	%	n	%	%	n	%
		within Type of Agent			within Type of Agent				
Sex	Female	78	29%	70%	116	43%	74%	194	73%
	Male	33	12%	30%	39	15%	25%	72	27%
	Prefer not to say	0	0%	0%	1	0%	1%	1	0%
	<i>Total</i>	111	42%	100%	156	58%	100%	267	100%
Age	18-25	13	5%	12%	4	2%	3%	17	6%
	26-35	60	22%	54%	44	16%	28%	104	39%
	36-45	16	6%	14%	31	12%	20%	47	18%
	46-55	10	4%	9%	38	14%	24%	48	18%
	56-65	12	4%	11%	39	15%	25%	51	19%
	<i>Total</i>	111	42%	100%	156	58%	100%	267	100%
Educational background	Accounting bachelor's degree (BS Accountancy)	47	18%	42%	72	27%	46%	119	45%
	Accounting post-bachelor's degree (Masters, PhD)	17	6%	15%	25	9%	16%	42	16%
	Non-accounting related bachelor's degree	28	10%	25%	33	12%	21%	61	23%
	Non-accounting related post-bachelor's degree (Masters, PhD)	19	7%	17%	26	10%	17%	45	17%
	<i>Total</i>	111	42%	100%	156	58%	100%	267	100%
Years in service	less than a year	4	2%	4%	2	1%	1%	6	2%
	1 - 5 years	37	14%	33%	28	10%	18%	65	24%
	6 - 10 years	33	12%	30%	25	9%	16%	58	22%
	10 -15 years	9	3%	8%	18	7%	12%	27	10%
	more than 15 years	28	10%	25%	83	31%	53%	111	42%
	<i>Total</i>	111	42%	100%	156	58%	100%	267	100%

Of the 267 surveyed respondents, 41.6% were concentrated agents, and 58.4% were distributed agents (**Figure 6**). The majority of the concentrated groups came from the DBM's operations group (budget and management bureaus), Finance Service, Administrative Services, Procurement Office, Internal Audit, other services, and regional offices. There were also representatives from the DOF and BTr. Distributed agents came from national government agencies and government corporations, details are provided in **Appendix 6**.

Figure 6. Type of Agent

Based on sex/gender, 73% were female and 27% male. Of which distributed agents were 43% females and 15% males, with less than 1% who preferred not to say. Among the concentrated agents, 29% were female, while 12% were male. Details are presented in **Figure 7**:

Figure 7. Types of Agent disaggregated by sex/gender

The most frequent age of respondents came from the 26-35 group, 22% concentrated and 16% distributed. Details are presented in **Figure 8** below:

Figure 8. By Age Group

In terms of years of experience, results revealed that 53% of the distributed-respondents have more than 15 years of experience compared to 25% of concentrated-respondents. Details are presented in **Figure 9** below:

Figure 9. Years of Experience

Respondents have different educational backgrounds but were categorized into two major groups: accounting and non-accounting graduates. 58% of the concentrated and 62% of the distributed agents were accountants. Of which, 15% and 16% have post-bachelor degrees, respectively. Details are presented in **Figure 10** below:

Figure 10. Type of Agent by educational background

Figure 11 revealed that 55% of respondents were aware of the BTMS. Awareness of other IFMIS-related systems is shown below:

Meanwhile, 23% of the respondents used the BTMS, presented in **Figure 12** below:

57% of concentrated-respondents received at least one training on IFMIS/BTMS, while 43% received none. 51% of distributed agents received at least one training, while 49% received none. Details are presented in **Figure 13** below:

Figure 13. IFMIS/BTMS Trainings received

5.2 Descriptive statistics

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics on the 267 respondents below:

	H1	H2	H3	H4
Mean	3.43	3.31	3.48	3.16
Median	3.4	3.33	3.45	3
Std. Deviation	0.39	0.62	0.42	0.56
Skew	0.18	0.2	0.2	-0.47
Kurtosis	1.14	0.36	1.72	3.3
Mean \pm Std.	3.43 \pm 0.39	3.31 \pm 0.62	3.48 \pm 0.42	3.16 \pm 0.56

Source: survey administered by the author

The implication of this table is further discussed in subsequent sections below. Based on the Jarque-Bera goodness-of-fit test, most survey items have skewness and kurtosis matching nonnormal distribution (**Appendix 7**). The Mann-Whitney U-test was used as the primary tool for analyzing the results, but the t-test was also employed as a reference to complement each other's weaknesses (de Winter & Dodou, 2010).

5.3 Hypotheses testing

This section covers the main findings of the study. First, results are presented per hypothesis following the framework established in Chapter 3. Quantitative data analysis was followed by a qualitative discussion of interview results connecting with the theoretical framework and previous literature.

5.3.1 Disrupted context

Under Hypothesis 1 (H1), we tested the established assumption that when a problem disrupts the context, agents question the capacity of incumbent structures and find weaknesses and loopholes in the existing systems, which create opportunities for reform. H1 assumed that distributed agents would less likely agree than concentrated agents that a problem disrupts the context. **Table 5** shows a summary of the results.

Table 5: Descriptive and inferential statistical results on H1

H1: Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than concentrated agents to agree that the context is disrupted by PFM-specific problems	Distributed Agents	Concentrated Agents	t-test, p values (p<0.05)	Mann Whitney U test, p values (p<0.05)
<i>Reform condition: context is disrupted by a problem</i>				
1) Resources (manpower, time, funds) are not maximized in the current/existing system;	49% agree	64% agree	0.127	0.091
2) Current/existing financial management and reporting systems are not integrated (i.e. systems are interlinked, interoperable, interfaced)	39% agree	35% agree		0.424
3) The new normal brought about by the COVID pandemic requires a more integrated (interlinked, interoperable, interfaced) IT systems	88% agree	96% agree		0.008
4) Maintaining the current/existing system already ensures proper allocation of financial resources	50% agree	49% agree		0.986
5) Maintaining the current/existing system may lead to possible corruption issues	19% agree	17% agree		0.546
Average			0.127	0.077

source: based on survey administered by the author

Item 1 showed that the concentrated agents had higher values ($Mdn = 4$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Here, distributed-respondents agreed less than concentrated-respondents (49% vs. 64%) that resources are not maximized in the current system. However, a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=7,658.5$, $p=.091$, $r= 0.1$.

Item 2 indicated that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed more than the concentrated-respondents that the current financial systems are not integrated (39% vs. 35%). However, a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=8,185.5$, $p=.424$, $r= 0.05$.

However, item 3 exhibited that the concentrated agents had equally high ($Mdn = 5$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 5$). Distributed-respondents agreed less than the concentrated-respondents that the pandemic disrupted the current context (88% vs. 96%). Confirming H1, a

Mann-Whitney U-Test showed the difference between the groups was **statistically significant**, $U=7,265.5$, $p=.008$, $r= 0.16$.

Item 4 showed that the concentrated agents had lower values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed group ($Mdn = 4$). Distributed-respondents agreed more than concentrated-respondents (50% vs. 49%) that current systems ensure the allocation of financial resources. However, a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=8,647.5$, $p=.986$, $r= 0$.

Lastly, item 5 results showed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed more than concentrated-respondents (19% vs. 17%) that the current system leads to corruption issues. However, a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=8,307$, $p=.546$, $r= 0.04$.

The average of all the items using parametric test showed that the concentrated agents have higher values ($M = 3.47$, $SD = 0.36$) than the distributed agents ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 0.4$). A two-tailed t-test for independent samples (equal variances assumed) revealed that the difference between groups that a problem disrupted the context was not statistically significant, $t(265) = 1.53$, $p = .127$, 95% confidence interval [-0.02, 0.17].

5.3.1.1 Analysis and Discussion

Because of the overall statistical insignificance in the difference in the perception of both groups that context is disrupted by PFM-specific problems, we cannot confirm that distributed agents would limit the success of IFMIS/BTMS. Nevertheless, the results contradict test assumptions when the variables are specific to IFMIS/BTMS (financial reporting system issues). In items 2, 4, and 5, results displayed that distributed agents agreed more, contrary to our expectations. What does the result suggest?

These results highlighted a possible gap in the theoretical framework when applied to the Philippine context. As earlier described, the framework assumed that concentrated agents focused more on their PFM roles and oversight functions and distributed agents on their primary mandate. For example, DPWH focuses on road infrastructure activities while DepEd on basic education

mandates. This may not be the case here. The results suggested that, first, either of the groups can have similar or closely associated perceptions with one another due to overlapping roles, as earlier studies pointed out (Berman,2016, Brillantes & Lorenzo, 2021). For example, concentrated agencies (DBM, BTr) can also be an implementing agency in the character of a distributed group, and distributed agencies (DPWH, DepEd) can think like a PFM concentrated agency in managing PFM-related activities. While Andrews argued that "PFM-specific problems would likely not generate as much concern" (Andrews, 2014, p.11) among distributed agencies, the results in items 2, 4, and 5 suggested otherwise. There is merit in Andrews' supposition that we should dissuade the idea that there is only one government. However, we cannot ignore the possibility that overlapping and blurred demarcation in government functions may lead to a similar group thinking/behavior (Andrews, 2014, Brillantes & Lorenzo,2021).

Secondly, within concentrated agencies, diversity persists. It might be flawed to assume, as Andrew's theory suggested (i.e., concentrated agents supports reform more), that they will perceive things similarly, particularly when a unit have different age groups and educational background. It may be recalled that the DBM and BTr were pilot agencies used in implementing BTMS, wherein 58% are accountants, and the rest have different backgrounds with age differences (**Table 3**). Our results showed that these concentrated-respondents working in the finance service, cash, and accounting units of DBM perceived reform conditions for IFMIS/BTMS as a distributed agent would. We found that they believed there was no problem with the current/existing setup. They claimed that there were already enough fiscal controls in compliance with existing DBM and COA rules that minimize the risk of inefficient use of resources and corruption. One respondent further quipped that "*the use of BTMS was redundant on our part, given that we are also required to prepare reports using the e-NGAS.*" Respondents who agreed to this notion were found to be accountants aged 26 and above, meaning that this group of concentrated agents was always dealing with the COA and had been using the e-NGAS in their current functions for years.

Perhaps, the result suggested that there can be subcategories in a concentrated unit, i.e., those supportive of new reforms vs. existing systems. Finance people might think differently from the planning and IT offices of a particular agency/office. These important variations due to age, length of experience, and educational background provided credence to Andrew's theory that both groups might have different intellectual influences and organizational experiences. However, such distinction did not prevent overlaps of perceptions among concentrated agents.

One of our key informants provided a crucial factor why concentrated agents supported the status quo more than the distributed agents, contrary to H1:

“because COA imposed e-NGAs and everybody's afraid of COA. In any ERP/GRP system, the core of a financial system is the accounting system. Everything emanates from the accounting records...There is always this resistance to doing something different and getting out of your comfort zone. Ok. Sanay na ako dito tapos ipagagawa mo sa akin ito (I'm used to this and you will ask me to do it). Second, you're asking them to do it (BTMS) and e-NGAs at the same time. Why so? because you have to familiarize yourself with the new system but you cannot abandon the old way of doing things. Not until you're sure that you can do it with the other. Then you're not going to drop the previous one. In the case of BTr, and DBM, who are loyal e-NGAs users, they find it doubly troublesome to encode in the BTMS and yet encode in the e-NGAS at the same time.”

Nevertheless, we found a statistically significant difference between the two groups in item 3. This result confirmed that the distributed agents less likely agreed than the concentrated agents that the pandemic disrupted the context. During the pandemic, respondents were caught by the longest lockdown in the country despite the need to continue working, as in the case of Korea (Jeong & Hwang, 2021). Both groups felt the need for integrated systems that could operate remotely and provide consolidated data urgently. Distributed agents, however, less likely agreed because, as Andrews' theory suggested, they were more preoccupied with their particular agency concerns.

While exogenous shocks like Covid highlighted weaknesses in the current system, such disruption could not guarantee optimal support of IFMIS/BTMS to resolve the fragmented IT systems. Other conditions must be considered, which we dealt with in subsequent sections.

5.3.1.2 Neutral answers

The average neutral score of the five items under H1 was 38% which means that more than a third of the respondents either have no opinion or an extreme opinion on the first reform condition. Based on qualitative prodding among respondents on why they answered neutral, results showed that it was due to the lack of awareness of the effects of current/existing systems and the BTMS in resource management. One respondent claimed that Project Management Office only has the data to see the effect of IFMIS on resource management. Thus, they cannot make a categorical position

on items 1 and 4. On whether existing systems may lead to corruption issues (item 4), one respondent claimed that corruption may or may exist despite having a new system “*depending on the use of the personnel involved, despite having various controls.*”

5.3.2 Legitimacy of Incumbent Institutions

The second Hypothesis (H2) assumes that when agents believe that incumbent rules are weakened and lost legitimacy, agents are open to the idea of reforms. Andrews (2014) suggested that distributed agents preferred decentralized hiring and revenue management while concentrated agents preferred centralized. The distributed group would prefer the old ways, and the concentrated group would prefer the reforms (Andrews, 2014). It was also assumed that distributed agents think their functions and budgeting are more political, while concentrated agents consider their functions and budgeting more technical. We tested these assumptions, and the results are provided in **Table 6** below.

Table 6: Descriptive and inferential statistical results on H2

H2: Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than the concentrated agents to agree that the incumbent PFM rules have lost legitimacy	Distributed Agents	Concentrated Agents	t-test, p values (p<0.05)	Mann Whitney U test, p values (p<0.05)
<i>Reform condition: Incumbents/Rules are weakened, agents reject incumbent logic</i>				
1) Hiring should be centralized, not delegated to local/lower units (i.e regional heads/officers, provincial, municipal offices)	34% agree	30% agree	0.65	0.202
2) Authority to manage revenue collections should be centralized, not delegated to local/lower units (i.e regional heads/officers, provincial, municipal offices)	40% agree	48% agree		0.868
3) The budget process is more technical than political	64% agree	60% agree		0.976
Average			0.65	0.618

Source: survey administered by the author

Item 1 results revealed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed more than concentrated-respondents (34% vs. 30%) on centralized hiring. However, a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=7,888.5$, $p=.202$, $r= 0.08$.

Item 2 showed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). While results confirmed that distributed-respondents were less likely to agree than concentrated-respondents (40% vs. 48%), a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant $U=8,560.5$, $p=.868$, $r= 0.01$.

Item 3 revealed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 4$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 4$). Distributed-respondents agreed more than concentrated-respondents (64% vs. 60%), but a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=8,640$, $p=.976$, $r= 0$.

The average of the items under H2 using a parametric test exhibited that the concentrated-respondents has lower values ($M = 3.29$, $SD = 0.61$) than the distributed-respondents ($M = 3.32$, $SD = 0.62$). A two-tailed t-test for independent samples (equal variances assumed) showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $t(265) = -0.45$, $p = .65$, 95% confidence interval [-0.19, 0.12].

5.3.2.1 Analysis and Discussion

Given the H2 result of statistical insignificance, we cannot confirm that the difference in the perception of both groups that incumbent rules are weakened or have lost their legitimacy would limit the success of IFMIS.

However, the results presented unexpected findings. First, we found that distributed-respondents agreed more than concentrated-respondents that hiring should be centralized. Perhaps this is because in the Philippine setup, hiring processes is highly centralized since civil service laws govern it. As such, it was standardized to begin with, and distributed-respondents cannot do much about whether they want it done at the local level because of the existing norms on hiring. Second, while distributed-respondents agreed less than concentrated-respondents on centralized revenue management, the same is governed by existing laws/rules. Third, distributed-respondents saw their day-to-day transactions involving the budget process as more technical, contrary to the established assumption that it is more political.

As discussed in our literature review and theoretical framework, the unexpected results may be attributable to cultural factors. Cultural factors formed a huge part of the hidden informal rules in

the iceberg metaphor of institutional change theory (Andrews, 2014). Also, Berman (2016) found a close-knit family tie in the Philippines, a cultural norm that has solidified even in the public sector/workplace.

In this case, both groups might have more similarities than differences. Our results have shown proportionate levels of educational background and similar functions. Distributed-respondents were the extension of concentrated agencies (DBM, DOF, BTr, and COA) and were responsible for relaying PFM rules to their non-PFM colleagues. They were the focal persons of every PFM activity within their respective units. Maybe, distributed-respondents perception of the tested variables could be akin to a concentrated group “thinking.” The respondents in Andrews' study are budget forum attendees who are budgeters, accountants, and auditors who are focused mainly on their agency mandates. While the same category was included in this research, the distributed-respondents, in this case, were not just one-time representatives. They participated in the budget forums annually. They coordinate with counterpart concentrated agents regularly, if not daily, for monitoring and submitting reports involving the budget. Next to their families, they have a close-knit relationship with their work networks, and here transactional relationships are highly valued (Berman, 2016). One respondent mentioned how things were facilitated by maintaining good relationships (“*I scratch your back, you scratch mine*”) with their counterparts in other agencies.

In this regard, our evaluation of H2 suggested that the insignificant difference between the two groups' perceptions may be due to cultural norms, i.e., similar thinking due to existing functions (accounting, budget) of both groups, and highly valued transactional relationships. However, we did not acquire enough data to categorically argue that this portion of the institutional iceberg metaphor has been substantially weakened to expect both groups to support or limit the IFMIS reform. Therefore, we need to investigate other reform conditions.

5.3.2.2 Neutral answers

32% of the survey results for H2 were neutral answers. Interview results revealed safe positioning in the survey because they were either not fully aware of all processes within the budget process. Thus, they could not specifically determine which particular context they were being asked. One respondent argued that *the “budget process was really technical but sometimes during the approval processes there is political aspect that cannot be avoided.”* Therefore, decision points vary per situation and cannot be rightfully captured in one setting. Methodologically, these results indicated

the need for a longitudinal design to be more accurate in capturing perceptions since it changes from time to time (Weber & Weber, 2001). Also, despite the pilot test of the survey, particular survey questions remained vague for the respondents, which could be improved in subsequent research.

5.3.3 IFMIS as a legitimate and viable alternative

Our third hypothesis (H3) postulated that both groups differ in perception of the legitimacy and viability of IFMIS given existing institutional arrangements. We tested the group difference with 11 dependent variables. The results are provided in **Table 7** below.

Table7: Descriptive and inferential statistical results on H3

H3: Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely than concentrated agents to consider IFMIS as a legitimate and practical reform alternative;	Distributed Agents	Concentrated Agents	t-test, p values (p<0.05)	Mann Whitney U test, p values (p<0.05)
<i>Reform condition: IFMIS is seen as a legitimate and a viable alternative</i>				
1) Implementing agencies/units tend to resist the application of IFMIS/BTMS	25% agree	48% agree	0.137	0.001
2) IFMIS, or its scaled-down version (BTMS) is the right reform solution	42% agree	35% agree		0.427
3) Existing systems/procedures should be improved (improve what exists rather than a comprehensive replacement)	82% agree	89% agree		0.142
4) Existing systems/procedures should be replaced (comprehensive change of procedures and processes driven by information technology)	43% agree	43% agree		0.662
5) Systems developed in-house (locally, based on existing systems upgrades) work better than commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) platforms (ready-made available for purchase in commercial market)	53% agree	65% agree		0.055
6) Existing legal arrangements (Executive Order No.55, s.2011) is sufficient for the effective implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	30% agree	31% agree		0.973
7) There is a need for institutionalization of BTMS and IFMIS-related reforms through legislative enactment	53% agree	69% agree		0.022
8) Current/existing systems arrangements (technical, non-technical capacities, and business processes) prevent the successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	47% agree	53% agree		0.433
9) The current/existing capacities of administrators (i.e. approver, reviewer, heads of agencies, bureaus, divisions) to implement IFMIS/BTMS are insufficient	47% agree	45% agree		0.125
10) The current level of political will of administrators (i.e. approver, reviewer, heads of agencies, bureaus, divisions) prevents higher chances of IFMIS/BTMS' successful implementation	52% agree	54% agree		0.571
11) The political environment is favorable to the successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	38% agree	41% agree		0.853
Average			0.137	0.174

Source: survey administered by the author

Item 1 results showed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Here, distributed-respondents were less likely to agree than the concentrated-respondents that implementing agencies resisted the implementation of IFMIS (25% vs. 48%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was **statistically significant**, $U=6,258$, $p<.001$, $r= 0.25$.

Item 2 revealed that the concentrated group had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed more than the concentrated-respondents that the IFMIS through the BTMS was the right reform solution (42% vs. 35%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=8,224.5$, $p=.427$, $r= 0.05$.

Item 3 results showed concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 4$) than the distributed group ($Mdn = 4$). While distributed-respondents were less likely to agree than concentrated-respondents that existing procedures should be improved (82% vs. 89%), Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=7,821$, $p=.142$, $r= 0.09$.

Item 4 displayed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the Distributed group ($Mdn = 3$). Both groups equally agreed at 43%. A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=8,396$, $p=.662$, $r= 0.03$.

Item 5 results revealed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 4$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 4$). Distributed-respondents were less likely to agree that custom-built IFMIS works better than COTS (53% vs. 65%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between them was not statistically significant, $U=7,543$, $p=.055$, $r= 0.12$.

Item 6 showed that concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed less on the sufficiency of existing legal bases (30% vs. 31%). However, a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between them was not statistically significant, $U=8,639.5$, $p=.973$, $r= 0$.

Item 7 results indicated that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 4$) than the distributed group ($Mdn = 4$). Distributed-respondents agreed less than the concentrated-respondents on the need for legislation to institutionalize IFMIS/BTMS (53% vs. 69%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was **statistically significant**, $U=7,311$, $p=.022$, $r= 0.14$. Thus, the results confirmed the difference in perception of both groups.

Item 8 revealed that the concentrated agents had higher values ($Mdn = 4$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed less than the concentrated-respondents that the current system setup prevents the successful implementation of IFMIS (47% vs. 53%). However, a Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between them was not statistically significant, $U=8,209$, $p=.433$, $r= 0.05$.

Item 9 showed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed more than concentrated-respondents that the current capacity of administrators to implement IFMIS/BTMS was insufficient (47% vs. 45%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=7,764$, $p=.125$, $r= 0.09$.

Item 10 results also revealed that the concentrated agents had equally high values ($Mdn = 4$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 4$). Distributed-respondents agreed less than concentrated-respondents that the current level of political will prevents the success of IFMIS (52% vs. 54%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between them was not statistically significant, $U=8,330$, $p=.571$, $r= 0.03$.

Finally, item 11 showed that the concentrated agent had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed agents ($Mdn = 3$). However, distributed-respondents agreed less than concentrated-respondents that the political environment is favorable for the success of IFMIS (38% vs. 41%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=8,552.5$, $p=.853$, $r= 0.01$.

The average for H3 items using a parametric test indicated that the concentrated group has higher values ($M = 3.52$, $SD = 0.44$) than the distributed group ($M = 3.44$, $SD = 0.4$). A two-

tailed t-test for independent samples (equal variances assumed) showed that the difference between them was not statistically significant, $t(265) = 1.49$, $p = .137$, 95% confidence interval [-0.03, 0.18].

5.3.3.1 Analysis and Discussion

Given H3 results of statistical insignificance overall, we cannot confirm that distributed agents would limit the success of IFMIS/BTMS. However, our results provided different perspectives on the matter.

Drivers of successful PFM reform: Context

In the existing literature, Peterson (2010) pointed out the importance of understanding the context as a driver of successful PFM reforms. Context includes understanding the political factors (Peterson, 2010). The survey results indicated that the majority of the agents perceived that political will was weak (52% distributed-respondents, 54% concentrated-respondents), which created skepticism about the success of IFMIS/BTMS. While the result aligned with Andrews' premise that distributed agents would be more skeptical, we found that the limitation is mainly due to concentrated agents.

Results based on interviews revealed that there was no strong political will from the higher authorities. Quoting our key informant:

"since this belongs to previous administration the one who took over did not understand or appreciate the rationale for the system as much as the previous administration did. I'm even talking here about the Secretaries themselves. The one who push this was even during the time of Secretary Boncodin, then Secretary Abad. Now when the new set of Secretaries came in, they came in from the cold. They do not know why this project is urgent, they do not appreciate the value of this project."

Political will has been the primary factor for success/failure in the case of neighboring ASEAN countries (Joshi et al.,2020). While Peterson (2006) argued that in the case of Ethiopia, only middle-managers were needed, the Philippine case was found to be more complicated. One concentrated-respondent strongly claimed that *"political will is the key to successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS."*

Maybe, political will could have been a major factor in the IFMIS' success in the Philippines should there have been a renewed commitment by the current and subsequent leadership. In terms of legal bases, the results showed that EO 55 was insufficient, and there is a need for legislation to make IFMIS/BTMS more viable. Should there have been political will, the executive, through the President and cabinet secretaries, could have lobbied in Congress to pass the Budget Reform Bill (BRB) that would institutionalize IFMIS and other reforms. EO 55 was only an executive issuance and covered only the executive branch (excluding legislative, judiciary, and constitutionally fiscal autonomous groups like COA). While EO 55 included COA as a member, once COA flexed its right as an autonomous body, EO 55 will no longer be enforceable to them. *"COA itself nominally supported the project but functionally did not"* (Magsino, personal communication, August 5, 2022). To date, the enthusiasm to pass the BRB pending in Congress has yet to be seen.²²

Unexpectedly, results showed that distributed-respondents were more welcoming to having BTMS. Some distributed-respondents were very hopeful about continuing the BTMS. Others wanted BTMS to be fully implemented in their agencies and to give them a refresher course to maximize its use effectively. This is contrary to some of the concentrated-respondents who viewed BTMS as a failure and would rather have e-NGAS (system by COA) be improved than revive the BTMS. The response of our key informant is very telling:

"In the case of DSWD, they don't have a choice because they don't have any other system. They started with the BTMS and that served their purpose. They were not using e-NGAS before. Now DepEd is similarly situated. DepEd also wanted to use it (BTMS) because it is the only system they have. They have to learn it and use it. But in the case of BTr, and DBM, who are loyal e-NGAS users, they find it doubly troublesome to encode in the BTMS and yet encode in the e-NGAS at the same time."

²² <https://cpbrd.congress.gov.ph/173-resources/for-legislators/17th-congress-legislative-agenda-tracker/agenda-and-briefers/795-budget-reform-act>

Drivers of successful PFM reform: Ownership

Related to context is ownership. It involves the strong involvement of the administration and domestic decision-makers (Peterson, 2010). However, in the case of the Philippines' IFMIS/BTMS, there remains an issue of lack of genuine ownership of BTMS. One key informant propounded:

“comparing our government system from the others, inherently government is fragmented. Fragmented because revenue and expenditure are being managed by two separate departments [DOF and DBM]. In other countries, under the DOF both revenue and expenditure are managed within the same department. Now, if you can look at private sector companies they manage their financial statements as one entity. As a matter of fact, they don't manage income and expense separately. They manage the bottom-line... What happens when you manage expense and revenue separately? The KPIs (key performance indicators) of each one is different. Your revenue, a specific performance indicator is a percentage of collection. And I will reward if you meet a certain target and I will punish you if you don't meet the target. But that's the only thing they [DOF] are looking at, revenue.”

The BTMS tried to resolve this fragmentation by consolidating income and expense in the same database to actively manage the bottom-line at any time. In this case, the government aimed to manage finances like the private company does. However, this is difficult to hurdle in the case of the Philippines. As recounted by our key informant:

“Now, I tell you if there is such a solution and there is such as a tool to carry out this function who owns it in the government? The answer is, none. Because nobody in this government manages the bottom-line. So who owns the BTMS, nobody...From the very start, I have this principle that we don't build something unless somebody owns it. You don't build a house only because you want to have to build a house because somebody asked you to do it anyway and after you finish the house you turn it over to the owner. The BTMS is finished I don't know to whom to turn it over to. It's not the DOF because it is only interested in the revenue, it is not DBM because it is only interested in the URS (Unified Reporting System). It is not BTr because BTr cannot even use it because the data in it is not complete. BTr will only be able to use the tool when it sees the entire government but as we are rolling it out agency per agency and building up a database that tool is

incomplete. So BTr doesn't see it as a useful tool. So asked me, who owns it? Nobody, nobody does."

While in previous administrations, there was a very strong connection between DBM, DOF, BTr, and COA to implement IFMIS. As evident in the COA's lack of participation in this study, the COA seemed hands-off now on this reform, primarily because they are a constitutionally independent institution, as such mandating them requires legislation, if not constitutional changes, and they have a competing system (e-NGAs). As observed by respondents, the COA was also improving its e-NGAs, which are 95% complete, more responsive to users, and much closer to the envisioned IFMIS under the PFM roadmap. This cast further doubts on the BTMS, given our findings that BTMS seemed to lack ownership, whereas COA fully owns existing alternative systems like e-NGAs.

Drivers of successful PFM reform: Purpose and Strategy

Another factor that we tested concerns the idea of purpose. Purpose pertains to whether one implements an advanced reform through international best practices or basic reforms (Peterson, 2010, Schick, 1999). IFMIS is deemed an advanced reform. As we would recall, IFMIS was a recommendation from the World Bank and the result of a PEFA assessment in the Philippines. Literature showed how World Bank advocated for IFMIS pressuring other countries to implement such advanced reform (Tetteh et al., 2021, Diokno, 1999, Combaz, 2015, Andrews, 2014).

The downside, as Peterson (2006) pointed out as the reason for IFMIS failure, was forcing governments to adopt a reform using COTS which “they would not otherwise make” and where the capacities in developing countries cannot match (Peterson, 2006,p.4). While most distributed-respondents (53%) favored custom-built/locally-developed IFMIS over COTS, our results also reflected how concentrated-respondents favored custom-built IFMIS (65%) more than COTS. Following our theory, if concentrated-respondents were more supportive of the reform, they were expected to prefer COTS more. In this case, they wanted to adopt a process change – incremental improvement of existing systems rather than replacing all of them with an innovation like IFMIS/BTMS, which end-users need to learn. Process change is what Peterson (2006) would describe as characteristic of a basic reform that often leads to success. This is contrary to the process innovation imposed by a COTS IFMIS, which led to failures in the long run (Peterson, 2006).

Moreover, our interview revealed how difficult it is to customize a COTS. While some respondents agreed that it was easier and cheaper to buy a COTS initially, they realized how difficult and costlier it was to customize a COTS system continuously. One distributed-respondent said, *“if COTS, it is cheaper, but in my knowledge, it often needs “reprogramming”/customization,”* to which our key informant confirmed: *“Definitely, the future versions of the software may or may not support your customizations anymore. And that is the first problem that we had with this particular solution.”*

We asked about the major consideration for availing COTS, and our key informant recalled that *“It is time. I mean it's the time it takes to put something in production because developing something will take a lot longer. I'll cite you the example of Korea, who develop their IFMIS, the dBrain, it took them ten years to develop. If you were in the shoes of Bon Moya and you only have three more years to serve the government because you are coterminous and you do not want this project to disappear because it belongs to this administration, you would have made the same decision.”*

Our key informant uttered that the intention was noble. However, this decision proved to be ineffective. As Peterson (2010) pointed out, the strategy needs to look at existing systems, improving them if found needed. However, as we discovered in the Philippines, time was the major factor. Having an instant COTS due to time constraints meant a lack of prior consideration of existing systems. Common themes that come out of the responses of both agents that fault failure of the current BTMS included (1) poor planning, (2) weak recognition of existing systems, and (3) not user-friendly, since it was commercially made, it was unfit for the existing processes of agencies. The decision could have saved the government many resources should the necessary strategy been utilized before purchasing the COTS.

5.3.3.2 Neutral answers

39% under H3 were neutral answers. Interviews with concentrated-respondents revealed that safe positioning in the survey was due to lack of familiarity with the issues, particularly when they were required to give perception beyond things they do not have control over, i.e., giving an opinion on the administrators and the other groups.

5.3.4 Agents are engaged in reform

The fourth hypothesis (H4) assessed the difference in perception of the engagement of agents in the design and development process of IFMIS/BTMS. H4 assumed that distributed agents were less likely involved than concentrated agents. **Table 8** presents the summary of the results.

Table 8: Descriptive and inferential statistical results on H4

H4: Distributed agents will limit IFMIS success because they are less likely to be engaged in IFMIS design than concentrated agents	Distributed Agents	Concentrated Agents	t-test, p values (p<0.05)	Mann Whitney U test, p values (p<0.05)
Reform condition: Agents are engaged behind reform				
1) Level of involvement in the IFMIS/BTMS reform design	90% not involved	89% not involved	0.098	0.06
2) Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were engaged enough in designing the system for IFMIS/BTMS	26% agree	29% agree		0.211
3) Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were not given enough opportunity to practice with and adapt the IFMIS/BTMS to context (agency needs, capacity constraints)	38% agree	37% agree		0.76
4) Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were given time to implement the proposed reform like BTMS	30% agree	38% agree		0.023
5) Were there enough capacity-building / training opportunities to use IFMIS/BTMS?	76% said no	80% said no		0.82*
Average			0.098	0.049

*Same p-value result when treating the dependent variable as nominal and using Chi² test,
Source: survey administered by the author

The results showed that the concentrated-respondents had higher values ($Mdn = 2$) than the distributed-respondents ($Mdn = 1$). However, results revealed that both groups thought they were not involved in the reform design (90% vs. 89%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups was not statistically significant, $U=7,623.5$, $p=.06$, $r= 0.12$.

Item 2 revealed that the concentrated-respondents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed-respondents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed less than concentrated-

respondents that the former were engaged enough in the design (26% vs. 29%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the agents was not statistically significant, $U=7,939$, $p=.211$, $r= 0.08$.

Item 3 results also indicated that the concentrated-respondents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed-respondents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed more than concentrated-respondents on sufficient time to practice the reform (38% vs. 37%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between them was not statistically significant, $U=8,480$, $p=.76$, $r= 0.02$.

Item 4 revealed that the concentrated-respondents had equally high values ($Mdn = 3$) than the distributed-respondents ($Mdn = 3$). Distributed-respondents agreed less than concentrated-respondents that the former was given enough time to implement the reform (30% vs. 38%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between the groups **was statistically significant**, $U=7,355.5$, $p=.023$, $r= 0.14$.

Item 5 showed that distributed-respondents agreed less than concentrated-respondents on whether there was enough capacity building for IFMIS/BTMS (76% vs. 80%). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that the difference between them was not statistically significant, $U=8,554.5$, $p=.82$, $r= 0.01$.

On the average, the results of the descriptive statistics show that the concentrated-respondents has higher values for the dependent variable H4 ($M = 3.23$, $SD = 0.43$) than the distributed-respondents ($M = 3.11$, $SD = 0.64$). A two-tailed t-test for independent samples (equal variances assumed) showed that the difference between concentrated and distributed agents with respect to the dependent variable H4 was not statistically significant, $t(265) = 1.66$, $p = .098$, 95% confidence interval [-0.02, 0.25].

5.3.4.1 Analysis and Discussion

Was there a difference between distributed and concentrated respondents' perceptions of engagement in reform design? Statistical test (t-test) showed that, on average, there was none. However, distributed-respondents agreed less than concentrated-respondents in the time given to

distributed agents to implement the reform, confirming our hypothesis. However, will the difference prove that distributed agents will limit IFMIS success?

Literature assumed that distributed agents are usually not involved in the design of IFMIS (Andrews, 2014). In the Philippine setting, results revealed that both groups of respondents were not even involved in the design. Earlier, we found that the BTMS was a COTS which meant that the design essentially was ready-made. Only a handful was involved in the selection process because the main factor was time in choosing COTS. As our key informant revealed in H3, alternatives like improving an existing system (e-NGAs) were not properly considered. The problem, as we have seen, is that the eventual customization suffered challenges during implementation and has proven to be costlier. According to one of our informants, the total cost now was Php1.6 billion or \$32 million from the original budget of Php495 million or \$9.5 million.

Having COTS as a platform for IFMIS/BTMS contributed to lack of process ownership even among concentrated agents. This result confirmed existing literature that lack of process ownership negatively affected the support of both groups since they were kept out of the loop in the design and even after pilot-testing and initial operation of the BTMS (Andrews, 2014). One distributed-respondent remarked that their suggestions were not considered to improve the BTMS. While they were included in the process improvement, their contribution was not eventually considered in decisions about the system. Nonetheless, said respondent still hoped that BTMS be continued. For the concentrated-respondents, the emerging pattern was to improve the existing e-NGAs instead of COTS BTMS.

The results further confirmed the importance of capacity building in implementing reforms. Distributed agents clamored for capacity building more than concentrated agents. Perhaps, due to the 53% distributed-respondents with more than 15 years of experience, they have been more technologically challenged with IFMIS/BTMS. One distributed-respondent claimed that most experienced personnel could no longer perform heavy computer-related functions and asked new staff and job-order employees to do the work. This result confirmed what Chêne (2009) found in most developing countries. Since there is low computer literacy and said gap grows as age increases, more capacity building is required to make IFMIS successful, particularly in this case where most finance people (budgeters, accountants, auditors) have been in the government service

for years and at the older age brackets. Otherwise, reforms will be limited (Chêne, 2009, Andrews, 2014).

One key informant clarified that capacity building must focus on administrative officers (*“because they're the ones who were supposed to use the system”*) and specific function only (*“the only thing you need to do here is to teach the driver how to drive a car. You don't have to tell them how the system operates. And that's where the difficulties are. Instead of teaching only the accounting people, you have to teach everyone how to use it”*). While we found this to be a practical and focused-approach, several respondents claimed that such an approach added to the problem because they perceived the matter as technical. However, the ones being trained are those in clerical/administrative positions.

Therefore, our results found that both agents were not engaged properly. It compromised support and resulted in limited success, but not attributable only to distributed agents (Chêne, 2009, Peterson, 2010, Andrews, 2014).

5.3.4.2 Neutral answers

49% or almost half under H4 were neutral answers. Similar reasons provided in other categories were found. Given these neutral answers, we reckon that it statistically diluted the difference between groups since the Mann-Whitney U-Test considers this in the rank-sum scores of the result.

CHAPTER VI

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATION

This final chapter concludes this study by summarizing key research findings and answering our research questions. This will also highlight the study's contributions and limitations, leading to a few recommendations.

6.1 Summary of Findings

The study aimed to assess perceptions of distributed and concentrated agents on IFMIS as PFM reform. If there are different perceptions between groups, we explored what explains them and how this relates to the institutional change theory and existing literature.

First, we asked how government agents' perceptions on IFMIS as a PFM reform differ given several reform conditions (four hypotheses) set in Andrews' study. Results showed an interesting variety of opinions ranging from the usefulness of IFMIS/BTMS to challenges encountered while using the system and whether IFMIS/BTMS was successfully implemented. Of the 22 variables studied, results revealed statistical significance in the difference of perception in four variables, which means that the hypotheses were confirmed in the following conditions: (1) distributed agents were less likely than concentrated agents to agree that context is disrupted because of the pandemic, (2) viability of reform was affected by resistance in the application of the BTMS and (3) need for legislation to institutionalize BTMS, and (4) distributed agents were not given enough time to implement the reform. We found no statistically significant difference with the rest of the 18 variables.

Secondly, we asked what explains the difference between the two groups, if any. Results revealed interesting factors and dimensions considering the Philippines experience. For one, eight variables tested in this research showed distributed agents would support the IFMIS/BTMS more than the concentrated agents, contrary to Andrews' hypotheses. This unexpected result indicated a possible gap in the theoretical framework such that framing a group perception might be porous given the overlapping functions in the government and since there remains the possibility of similarities of perception across the two groups and diversity within each group. As we have found, this was

perhaps due to the cultural norms in the workplace, i.e., close-knit family relationships in the public sector and highly valued transactional relationships, present among the respondents.

Finally, we evaluated whether these differences in perception would confirm that distributed agents would limit the success of IFMIS. Because of the varying results identified above and the unique circumstances of the Philippine context, we deduced the answer as inconclusive. However, the study found that based on the survey results, interviews, and analysis of existing literature, the following main factors limited the success of IFMIS in the country: (1) lack of political will and (2) lack of ownership among concentrated agencies themselves, (3) the problematic purchase of COTS IFMIS/BTMS, and (4) poor management strategy.

6.2 Conclusion

In light of these results, findings taken as a whole are indicative rather than conclusive. We do not have enough empirical evidence to categorically support that distributed agents would limit the success of reform in the case of the Philippines. We do not claim that the original findings of Andrews are erroneous. The difference in the result is probably attributable to a specific case study design that focuses on a particular PFM reform such as IFMIS and a specific case like the Philippines. The different kinds of samples used in this case yield additional findings worthy of consideration but remain inconclusive in the presence of certain limitations.

Nonetheless, the emerging patterns in the Philippines contributed to understanding the difference (and similarity) between the two types of agents and how they perceived IFMIS as a PFM reform. Distributed-respondents agreed more to have IFMIS/BTMS as they needed the reform. However, the concentrated-respondents questioned the viability of BTMS often and suggested improving e-NGAS instead. Perhaps, the IFMIS/BTMS have limited success not because of the distributed agents but due to the circumstances within the realm of concentrated agents to where the above limiting factors are attributable. These nuances indicated that it is complicated to categorize certain group characteristics, particularly government personnel whose functions frequently overlap.

While the results supported the idea that there remain no categorical rules that could guarantee IFMIS implementation's outcome, we found bread crumbs in our investigation that we deem significant to various stakeholders:

1. The results of this study could help our PFM agencies' decision-makers to revisit existing systems, acknowledging the roles of both groups in the holistic implementation of IFMIS.
2. Donor agencies may use this as a reference in understanding country context to balance their advocacy to push IFMIS in developing countries.
3. This research may serve as a footprint to follow with more case studies to deepen understanding of how agents contribute to the success of IFMIS or any other PFM reform and improve theoretical built-up involving existing government programs and projects.

6.3 Limitations

Methodological limitations based on design, representativeness, and power to predict solutions are among the identified weaknesses of this research.

The use of purposive sampling limited the representativeness of the study. The samples pertain primarily to those two categories specifically identified by Andrews (2014) with characteristics relevant to the research question. Thus, the findings cannot be generalized to all public sector agents in the Philippines. One lesson we can draw from the results is to consider the different representative of each group. Perhaps, if the respondents from the distributed agency were the engineer from the DPWH, a teacher from DepEd, and a social worker from DSWD, the story could have been different.

While the researcher perceived that a longitudinal data approach could have assessed better the varying perceptions of each agent by conducting pre and post-project implementation surveys, due to time limitations, cross-section data was utilized instead. Significant neutral answers might also influence the results that could be minimized through longitudinal survey and test-retest method, which the study could not utilize.

6.4 Recommendation

For future research

We hope that the above limitations will be mitigated through subsequent action research with an improved methodology. Because this study largely stemmed from Andrews's theory on why distributed end-users often limit the success of an externally-supported PFM reform, we need more research to replicate this study using other related PFM reforms and country experiences.

In sampling respondents, one might venture into different participants such as technically non-PFM practitioners within the distributed agencies and straying up to the lowest governance unit if possible. Since the tool used is experimental and patterned with Andrew's study, future researchers may administer a more sophisticated method to capture group distinction and thinking on a particular reform. It would be interesting to add focus group discussions among select participants in the methodology to clarify and test pre-conceived notions and findings.

In terms of crucial factors that other studies could explore, we recommend covering political leadership and how they influence the success or failure of a particular reform. If the government needs the benefit a particular reform offers, and agents are supportive, why is the leadership not pushing hard for it?

For policy recommendation

Understanding the role of agents in a reform outcome is a hit or miss since PFM undertakings often involve trial and error. First, we recommend a comprehensive analysis by the decision-makers of context, ownership, purpose, and strategy to minimize the risk of failure since they serve as useful drivers of reform. Second, we encourage strengthening the political will by our PFM leaders to lobby the legislation of the BRB that would institutionalize PFM reforms such as IFMIS to increase its viability. Third, continuous documentation and evaluation of lessons learned from past experiences through the perspectives of system end-users should be encouraged. This way, subsequent leaders would have reference/materials for decision-making and be encouraged to have process ownership. Fourth, while the COTS platform has advantages, we recommend improving and supporting existing systems instead of buying a new COTS, given its practicality, ownership, and supportability.

The promise of IFMIS would continue to entice a government that wants to improve. However, improvement needs to consider many things and weigh many factors. As this study showed, there is no proven formula for success but there is an opportunity for improvement. We must recognize the importance of learning from past lessons to improve future policies. It may be a hit or miss, success or failure, but we must continuously try and get better each time.

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Appendix 1. Approval to conduct survey

July 8, 2022

SECRETARY AMENAH F. PANGANDAMAN

Department of Budget and Management
Gen. Solano St., San Miguel, Manila

Thru: Atty. Andrea Celene M. Magtalas
Director, Administrative Services

Dear **Secretary Pangandaman**,

This is to respectfully request permission to conduct a survey to the DBM employees as part of my thesis requirement for the Advanced Master in Development Evaluation and Management Program at the University of Antwerp in Belgium.

Said survey aims to assess perceptions of concentrated agents (personnel from PFM oversight agencies like the DBM) and distributed end-users (budget officers, accountants, auditors, and other system users of implementing line agencies) that influence the dynamics of PFM reform outcome, particularly in the case of Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS).

The survey will be administered via email blast from July 12, 2022, and will end on the closing day of business hours of July 22, 2022. The data collected will remain confidential and used solely for academic purposes. Attached is a copy of the survey for reference.

Your approval to conduct this survey will be greatly appreciated. Thank you.

Best regards,

Digitally signed by Johnry
Castillo
Date: 2022.07.08 10:34:53
+02'00'

Johnry Castillo

Advanced Master in Development Evaluation and Management
Institute of Development Policy
University of Antwerp

APPROVED

DISAPPROVED

JUL 14 2022

AMENAH F. PANGANDAMAN

Secretary, Department of Budget and Management

Appendix 1a. Survey Questionnaire

IFMIS, a hit or miss?: Gov't agents' perception analysis of Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS):

I am inviting you to participate in this research by completing the following survey. This research aims to explore the role of agents in the success or failure of a Public Financial Management (PFM) Reform. In this study, we look at the case of IFMIS, or its down-scaled version BTMS. IFMIS is an integrated ICT solution that aims to collect and organize financial information of all government agencies for government-wide consolidation. The BTMS aims to integrate appropriations, allotments, cash allocations, commitments, obligations, disbursements, and reporting functions to eliminate multiple stand-alone systems; to have real-time online monitoring of appropriations, allotments, obligations and disbursements, among others originally intended to be achieved by IFMIS.

The following questionnaire will take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete. Your participation is helpful to deepen our understanding of the dynamics of PFM reforms and identify opportunities to inform future PFM reforms and undertakings. The data collected will remain confidential and used solely for academic purposes.

* Required

1. Email *

Skip to question 2 *Skip to question 2*

Part 1. Demographic questions

2. Age *

Check all that apply.

- 18-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- 46-55
- 56-65

3. Sex *

Check all that apply.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

4. Current agency/office/unit *

5. Work experience *

Check all that apply.

- I am currently working in PFM oversight and attached agencies (DOF, DBM, COA) and have never worked anywhere else in my government career
- I am currently working in PFM oversight and attached agencies (DOF, DBM, COA) but I have worked in other government agencies as well
- I am currently working in a line/implementing agency but have worked in PFM oversight agencies (DOF, DBM, COA) before
- I am currently working in a line/implementing agency and have never worked in oversight PFM agencies (DOF, DBM, COA)

6. Years in service *

Check all that apply.

- less than a year
- 1 - 5 years
- 6 - 10 years
- 10 -15 years
- more than 15 years

7. Educational background *

Check all that apply.

- Accounting bachelor's degree (BS Accountancy)
- Accounting post-bachelor's degree (Masters, PhD)
- Non-accounting related bachelor's degree
- Non-accounting related post-bachelor's degree (Masters, PhD)

Part II.
Institutional
Change
and Reform
conditions

The previous 2010 PEFA assessment highlighted the gaps of fragmented ICT systems in various PFM processes, cash management, and accounting practices, coupled with the limited capacities of PFM practitioners.

In response, PFM oversight agencies (DBM, DOF/BTr, and COA) collaborated to institute reforms centered on developing a Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS). Over the years, the conceptual design for an IFMIS was developed, the Treasury Single Account (TSA) was installed to unify cash management, the Unified Accounts Code Structure (UACS) for all financial transactions was also adopted, and the capacity-building program of PFM practitioners started, among many other reforms implemented.

The IFMIS became the core automation solution that aims to collect and organize financial information of all government agencies to provide timely and comprehensive information on where public finances go.

However, several technological and non-technological factors prevented the government from proceeding with the rollout of GIFMIS as originally planned. The DBM pursued a minor core system to provoke less opposition (Fritz et al., 2017) through the Budget Treasury Management System (BTMS). This core system links budgeting execution and treasury cash management, among its many modules. However, the DBM announced in 2021 the indefinite suspension of the BTMS use and rollout because of the changes in the strategic direction of the envisioned IFMIS. On July 6, 2022, new Budget Secretary Amenah Pangandaman announced the possible relaunching of the BTMS, "We've made headway with our Budget and Treasury Management System (BTMS), but there is so much more we can do to further strengthen our integrated financial management information system (IFMIS)" (dbm.gov.ph)

Now this part will explore your perceptions on reform conditions that may influence the outcome of IFMIS/BTMS implementation in the country.

8. What type of IFMIS and its component apps are you aware of? *

Check all that apply.

- Budget Treasury Management Systems (BTMS)
- Unified Reporting System (URS)
- Unified Account Codes Structures (UACS)
- Treasury Single Account (TSA)
- Budget Cycle Analytics (BCA)
- Online Submission of Budget Proposals (OSBPs)
- Government Manpower Information Systems (GMIS)
- Other: _____

9. What type of IFMIS and its component apps have you used at work? *

Check all that apply.

- Budget Treasury Management Systems (BTMS)
- Unified Reporting System (URS)
- Unified Account Codes Structures (UACS)
- Treasury Single Account (TSA)
- Budget Cycle Analytics (BCA)
- Online Submission of Budget Proposals (OSBPs)
- Government Manpower Information Systems (GMIS)
- Other: _____

Instructions

For the following questions, please tick/choose only one option:

1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neutral 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree

10. Resources (manpower, time, funds) are not maximized in the current/existing system *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

11. Current/existing financial management and reporting systems are integrated (i.e. systems are interlinked, interoperable, interfaced) *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

12. The new normal brought about by the COVID pandemic requires a more integrated (interlinked, interoperable, interfaced) IT systems *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

13. Maintaining the current/existing system already ensures proper allocation of financial resources *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

14. Maintaining the current/existing system may lead to possible corruption issues *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

15. Existing systems/procedures should be improved (improve what exists rather than a comprehensive replacement) *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

16. Existing systems/procedures should be replaced (comprehensive change of procedures and processes driven by information technology) *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

17. Hiring should be centralized, not delegated to local/lower units (i.e regional heads/officers, provincial, municipal offices) *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

18. Authority to manage revenue collections should be centralized, not delegated to local/lower units (i.e regional heads/officers, provincial, municipal offices) *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

19. The budget process is more technical than political *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

20. Implementing agencies/units tend to resist the application of IFMIS/BTMS *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

21. IFMIS, or its scaled-down version (BTMS) is the right reform solution *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

22. If your answer in the question above is 1 (strongly disagree) or 2 (disagree), what do you recommend is a better alternative solution(s) other than IFMIS/BTMS? If your answer is 3 and above, please write N/A.

23. Systems developed in-house (locally, based on existing systems upgrade) work better than commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) platforms (ready-made available for purchase in commercial market) *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

24. Existing legal arrangements (Executive Order No.55, s.2011) is sufficient for the effective implementation of IFMIS/BTMS *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

25. There is a need for institutionalization of BTMS and IFMIS-related reforms through legislative enactment *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

26. Current/existing systems arrangements (technical, non-technical capacities, and business processes) prevents the successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

27. The current/existing capacities of administrators (i.e. approver, reviewer, heads of agencies, bureaus, divisions) to implement IFMIS/BTMS is insufficient *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

28. The current level of political will of administrators (i.e. approver, reviewer, heads of agencies, bureaus, divisions) prevents higher chances of IFMIS/BTMS' successful implementation *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

29. The political environment is favorable to the successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

30. Level of involvement in the IFMIS/BTMS reform design *

Check all that apply.

- Actively involved
- Not involved but committed (by virtue of office functions, I was consulted, part of the working group, etc))
- Not involved

31. Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies * were engaged enough in designing the system for IFMIS/BTMS

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

32. Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies * were not given enough opportunity to practice with, and adapt the IFMIS/BTMS to context(agency needs, capacity constraints)

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

33. Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were given time to implement the proposed reform like BTMS *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

34. Have there been capacity building activities related to IFMIS/BTMS? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No Skip to question 37
 Unaware Skip to question 37

35. If your answer to the question above is yes, have you participated in such trainings? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No Skip to question 37

36. How many trainings related to IFMIS/BTMS have you attended? *

Check all that apply.

- Once
 More than once
 None

Untitled Section

37. In your opinion, were there enough capacity building / training opportunities to use IFMIS/BTMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

38. If you have anything to add or comment, please indicate it here: *

Thank you for your participation!

The data collected will remain confidential and used solely for academic purposes.

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Google Forms

Appendix 2. Interview questions

Follow-Up Interview Guide for Online Survey Respondents

Before we start, I'd like to explain what we'll be doing during the interview, which will take no longer than 15 minutes, as well as answer any questions you might have. Basically, I'll ask you questions about your responses to our survey on IFMIS. With your permission, I'd like to record our interview as it will help me better focus on our conversation [pause for response; if subjects say no, then the interview will not be recorded].

Please note that you don't have to answer every question. This interview will be kept strictly confidential and your identity will remain anonymous when we write-up the results of the study. Upon completion of the study all records that contain personal identifiers will be shredded/deleted. Any questions before we begin?

Warm-up Questions (2mins)

How long have you been in__ and what's your function (establish rapport questions)?

Main Questions: (10 minutes)

- When you responded to our survey, you indicated **Neutral** answers, can I identify those and would you recall what did you think about that time, why was your answer neutral?
- What is IFMIS/BTMS trying to resolve and why?
- Why do you think the BTMS was suspended, what's the problem with BTMS based on your experience?
- What are your thoughts about the readiness of endusers like yourself, are you equipped to use the system?
- Have there been capacity building/training for BTMS? If so, have you encountered any problems? Do you think it is sufficient?
- Are the goals of IFMIS/BTMS met? Why or why not?

Closing:

Thank you very much for participating in our study. I appreciate your taking the time to talk with me.

Key informant Interviewer's Notes:

Before we start, I'd like to explain what we'll be doing during the interview, which will take no longer than 15 minutes, as well as answer any questions you might have. Basically, I'll ask you questions about the context and other factors considered in the implementation of IFMIS. We will also ask you about your thoughts on the findings of our survey on IFMIS. With your permission, I'd like to record our interview as it will help me better focus on our conversation [pause for response; if the subjects says no, then interview will not be recorded].

Please note that you don't have to answer every question. The authors and sources of data will be rightfully acknowledged and respect shall be maintained for the respondents who will provide valuable information and knowledge that will be gained from the study. Given this information, may I respectfully ask for your consent before we begin the interview. Any questions before we begin?

Warm-up Questions (2mins)

How long have you been in government service and your agency in particular?

Main Questions: (10 minutes)

CONTEXTUAL

Why was BTMS suspended? what do you think were the problems with the previous versions of BTMS? And IFMIS in general? Are these problems existing to date?

Is there some other software also in addition to BTMS which are co-existing either as legacy systems or filling the gaps created? If so, what is/are this software and what do they do? Are there any plans to integrate them? How?

ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS

Would you know the deciding factors on which platform to use, i.e off the shelf or custom-built? How was the decision to used COTS arrived at?

Was there a discussion about the use of COTS vs locally developed software?

What do you think was the deciding factor for them to use or purchase COTS?

Were changes to the existing business process from the COTS solutions large? How long did it take to reach consensus on the required changes to the existing process? How did it affect the system implementation overall?

Were legal changes needed to effect these changes? If they were, since it normally takes time to change laws how had this issue been handled so as to ensure continuous system implementation (interim solutions are adopted while legal changes are processed)

Did changes to business processes also change the organisational structure of Finance/Treasury?

Have there been capacity building/training for BTMS? If so, have you encountered any problems? Do you think it is sufficient?

TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS

What do you think is the role of platform for interconnectivity and how does it affect the implementation of IFMIS/BTMS?

Government after-thoughts about customization requirements (are they regretting now or feeling that the customization requirements were appropriate?)

PROCUREMENT

Have you encountered any procurement issues on IFMIS/BTMS? If so, what are those and how was it resolved?

POLITICAL

In the literature studies, political factor, ownership, political will come often, in our case in the BTMS, during the previous administration who is pushing for the reform?

In relation to that, is the government ready and capacitated to have the system?

From where did the motivation/stimulus come for the politicians to adopt the reform agenda?

Did implementing IFMIS become a political issue, if so how?

Any leader who spearheaded the process?

What is the ultimate requirement of PFM reform as far as FMIS is concerned? · Goals of the project (primary and secondary e.g. Improving efficiency, decrease delays etc.)

In terms of our PFM goals related to IFMIS, what has been met? What remains to be completed?

Was the previous version of BTMS a success/failure?

RESULTS VALIDATION QUESTIONS

in our findings conducted among the distributed agents and concentrated agents some see the disconnect between the BTMS as a tool into their business processes, what do you think about this?

There was even a mention from the survey that in terms of the capacity building, it only reaches the level of administrative officers, not the technical person, is that true?

May we get your opinion on this, some of the results are staying instead of BTMS why not improve the e-NGAS?

Given these features of the BTMS, was it actually reflected in the system itself?

That's what we actually try to also look at, why are the stakeholders actually not using it if the system is there and complete?

Do you think there's a difference, for example the staff resistance among DBM people and the staff resistance to use it among DPWH (line agencies, distributed groups)?

Does it mean each agency we will have to customize because they different business processes?

in the final analysis, in your assessment of the previous BTMS version, was it a success or failure and why?

Closing:

Thank you very much for participating in our study. I appreciate your taking the time to talk with me.

Appendix 3. Follow-up survey

Follow-up email interview / questionnaire

Hello,

Once again, thank you for participating in our IFMIS/BTMS survey. Your inputs are very valuable to this research. We just like to make a quick clarification on some of your responses and ask for additional information. We would appreciate your feedback on or before **August 5, 2022**.

- When you responded to our survey, you indicated **Neutral** (3) answers (attached is your survey response). Would you recall what did you think about that time, why was your answer neutral? Please indicate your comments per item with neutral answers and if possible in bullet form (there are no right or wrong answers here, we just want to dig deeper for more context).

Additional questions:

- What is IFMIS/BTMS trying to resolve and why?
- Why do you think the BTMS was suspended? What's the problem with BTMS based on your experience?
- What are your thoughts about the readiness of end-users like yourself, are you equipped to use the system?
- In your assessment, was the previous version of BTMS a success or a failure? Why or why not?
- What do you think should be done to maximize favorable outcome for IFMIS/BTMS?

Additional comments?

Please note that you don't have to answer every question. Your answers will be kept strictly confidential and your identity will remain anonymous when we write up the results of the study. Upon completion of the study all records that contain personal identifiers will be shredded/deleted.

Thank you.

	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Existing legal arrangements (Executive Order No.55, s.2011) is sufficient for the effective implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	0.5	0.73
There is a need for institutionalization of BTMS and IFMIS-related reforms through legislative enactment	0.13	0.75
Current/existing systems arrangements (technical, non-technical capacities, and business processes) prevents the successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	0.51	0.73
The current/existing capacities of administrators (i.e. approver, reviewer, heads of agencies, bureaus, divisions) to implement IFMIS/BTMS is insufficient	0.49	0.73
The current level of political will of administrators (i.e. approver, reviewer, heads of agencies, bureaus, divisions) prevents higher chances of IFMIS/BTMS' successful implementation	0.47	0.73
The political environment is favorable to the successful implementation of IFMIS/BTMS	0.47	0.73
Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were engaged enough in designing the system for IFMIS/BTMS	0.39	0.73
Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were not given enough opportunity to practice with, and adapt the IFMIS/BTMS to context (agency needs, capacity constraints)	0.36	0.73
Budget officers, accountants, auditors, and end-users from line/implementing agencies were given time to implement the proposed reform like BTMS	0.41	0.73
Hiring should be centralized, not delegated to local/lower units (i.e regional heads/officers, provincial, municipal offices)	0.1	0.76

Appendix 5. Ethical Considerations

In data gathering, the first part of the survey provided respondents with details and the purpose of the study. Respondents were requested to provide consent before proceeding with the survey. They were assured confidentiality at the beginning and the end of the data gathering activities. Respondents were provided a copy of their responses, and the summary results for validation. Key informants were also apprised of the study's objectives and were requested to consent to the interviews. All information and data were treated with the utmost confidentiality and used for academic purposes only.

Despite working for one of the agencies surveyed, the researcher remained independent and objective in analyzing the data gathered.

Appendix 6. List of respondents per agency/department

Concentrated Agents (PFM Committee Agencies)	Respondents
Department of Budget and Management (DBM)	95
Department of Finance (DOF)	9
Bureau of the Treasury (BTr)	7
<i>Sub-total, concentrated agents</i>	<i>111</i>
Distributed Agents	
Civil Service Commission	2
Department of Agriculture	2
Department of Education	14
Department of Energy	2
Department of Health	9
Department of Human Settlement	3
Department of Interior and Local Government	7
Department of Justice	7
Department of Labor and Employment	5
Department of National Defense	5
Department of Science and Technology	21
Department of Social Welfare and Development	3
Department of Tourism	2
Department of Trade and Industry	5
Department of Transportation	2
Government-owned or controlled corporations	37
Judiciary	5
Metro Manila Development Authority	2
National Defense College of the Philippines	6
National Economic Development Authority	5
Office of the President	8
Presidential Communications Operations Office	4
<i>Sub-total, distributed agents</i>	<i>156</i>
Total respondents	267

Appendix 7. Jarque-Bera Goodness-of-fit test

Column1	Resources	Current/e	The new	Maintaini	Maintaini
observations	267	267	267	267	267
skewness	-0.259220874	-0.4551202	-1.7286606	-0.4551202	-1.7286606
kurtosis	-0.269054215	-0.4917436	3.2373855	-0.1519086	-0.0428488
JB test	3.79553868	11.9076342	249.5753	9.4742016	132.99832
p-value	14.99%	0.26%	0.00%	0.88%	0.00%

Column1	Existing	Existing s	Hiring sh	Authority t	The buc
observations	267	267	267	267	267
skewness	-0.170127	-1.7286606	-0.1701268	0.023108675	-0.170127
kurtosis	1.9686931	-0.6673558	-0.7736929	-0.17626003	-0.421579
JB test	44.405715	137.932572	7.9474024	0.369390502	3.2652
p-value	0.00%	0.00%	1.88%	83.14%	19.54%

Column1	Impleme	IFMIS, o	Systems c	Existing i	There i	Currer
observations	267	267	267	267	267	267
skewness	0.023109	-1.140065	0.02310868	-1.1400654	-0.06735	-1.14007
kurtosis	-0.122731	1.363438	0.04083115	0.3977608	-0.04221	0.50665
JB test	0.191339	78.51979	0.0423109	59.598962	0.221665	60.6946
p-value	90.88%	0.00%	97.91%	0.00%	89.51%	0.00%

Column1	The cur	The c	The p	Budget of	Budget	Budget
observations	267	267	267	267	267	267
skewness	-0.06735	0.1255	-0.0673	0.12549393	-0.303274	-0.41488
kurtosis	-0.13183	0.3405	0.45529	0.21278006	0.044132	0.358664
JB test	0.395185	1.9909	2.50795	1.20450667	4.114548	9.090871
p-value	82.07%	37.0%	28.54%	54.76%	12.78%	1.06%